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MASTER THESIS

Pose Estimation of Dairy Cows

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Declaration of Authorship

I, Alexander SCHENDELMANN, declare that this thesis titled, "Pose Estimation of Dairy Cows" and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

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- Where I have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always given. With the exception of such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
- I have acknowledged all main sources of help.
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PARIS LODRON UNIVERSITY SALZBURG

Abstract

Faculty of Digital and Analytical Sciences

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Pose Estimation of Dairy Cows

by Alexander SCHENDELMANN

The growing demand for scalable, cost-effective livestock monitoring systems has prompted the exploration of Computer Vision-based solutions suitable for small-scale dairy farms. This thesis investigates real-time capable Pose Estimation models for dairy cows, focusing on their ability to generalize across diverse farm settings while maintaining inference speed and accuracy. A custom dataset, derived from real barn environments and annotated using the AP-10K keypoint scheme, was created to supplement existing public datasets. Three state-of-the-art models - ViTPose, RTMPose, and RTMO - were trained and evaluated using various strategies, including pre- and joint-training with domain-specific data. The models were assessed for accuracy, inference speed, and generalization capacity using both in-domain and out-of-domain benchmarks. Results indicate that while ViTPose yields slightly higher accuracy, RTMPose and RTMO offer competitive performance with significantly lower inference times, rendering them suitable for real-time applications. The findings demonstrate the potential of Pose Estimation for non-invasive behavioral monitoring and highlight the importance of fine-tuning with both public and custom datasets for generalizability and domain adaptation.

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Acronyms

ANN	Artificial Neural Network.
AP	Average Precision.
AP-10K	Animal Pose 10K.
APT-36K	Animal Pose Estimation and Tracking 36K.
APtv2	Animal Pose Estimation and Tracking Version 2.
AUC	Area Under Curve.
AwA	Animals with Attributes.
BN	Batch Normalization.
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network.
COCO	Common Objects in COntext.
DETR	Detection Transformer.
IoU	Intersection over Union.
KLD	Kullback-Leibler Divergence.
mAP	Mean Average Precision.
ML	Machine Learning.
MLE	Maximum Likelihood Estimation.
MLP	Multi Layer Perceptron.
OKS	Object Keypoint Similarity.
PCK	Percentage of Correct Keypoints.
R-CNN	Regions with CNN features.
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit.
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification.
RTMDet	Real-Time Models for object DETection.
RTMO	Real-Time Multi-Person One-Stage Pose Estimation.
RTMPose	Real-Time Multi-Person Pose Estimation.

SimCC	Simple Coordinate Classification.
ViT	Vision Transformer.
ViTPose	Vision Transformer Pose Estimation.
YOLO	You Only Look Once.

1 Introduction

This master thesis addresses real-time capable Pose Estimation of dairy cows contributing to livestock monitoring purely based on camera systems. First, the relevance of Computer Vision in agriculture is outlined in order to then finalize the objectives and the structure of this thesis.

1.1 Motivation

Industrialization has had an impact on almost all sectors, including agriculture [UN, 1966]. Using technology, farms can be scaled up to maximize efficiency and revenue. For instance, milk robots that not only milk the cows but also analyze the cows' individual health statuses are profitable for large farms. For traditional small-scale farmers, such an expensive investment does not pay off. However, without innovative technologies, it is difficult for them to keep up with the profit-driven industry. As a consequence, many small farms have closed down in the last two decades, which results in a drastic decrease in the number of dairy farms [Tergast, Hansen, and Weber, 2022].

This trend has significant implications for climate change. Most of the greenhouse gas emissions caused by agriculture can be traced back to industrial farms. Instead, ecologically friendly methods used by small farmers could reduce these emissions. This work is designed to counteract the current trend by providing easy and cost-effective solutions tailored for small-scale dairy farms. [Lin et al., 2011]

A promising approach for such an affordable solution is Computer Vision, which requires cameras only. Computer Vision is omnipresent in today's world, whether it's unlocking a smartphone using facial recognition or analyzing medical images to make initial diagnoses. Due to its power and scalability, it has also reached livestock farming. In contrast to many alternative sensing technologies, such as the use of implanted Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) chips [Barge et al., 2013], no hardware is required on the animal.

In livestock farming, Computer Vision can help to analyze animal behavior. For the farmer, the detection of unusual behavior is crucial. For instance, detecting diseases in an early stage is of great benefit to both the farmer's profit and animal welfare. Additionally, heat detection is highly profitable for the farmer, as it enables them to avoid missing the opportunity to inseminate the cows. To make such a system work,

several Computer Vision challenges must be solved. A complete processing pipeline is shown in Figure 1.1. [Qazi, Razzaq, and Iqbal, 2024]

FIGURE 1.1: Pipeline for Computer Vision-based livestock farming

The idea of the envisioned pipeline is that the farmer only needs a smartphone app that shows an overview of the health status of the individual cows. In case of unusual behavior, push notifications are to be sent via the app to intervene as soon as possible. To achieve this, the objects have to be detected first (see Section 2.2). For every detected object, its pose is to be estimated (see Section 2.3), it is to be tracked from frame to frame, and it must be assigned to one of the cows that are initially entered in the database (Re-Identification). Having obtained the tracks and poses of the individual cows, activities such as lying, standing, and walking can be classified. Over time, the course of these activities can be used to classify the health status of the individual cows. For instance, high activity usually indicates heat, while low activity can be an indicator of diseases such as lameness.

This thesis focuses on Pose Estimation. Object Detection, Object Tracking and Re-Identification of dairy cows for small-scale farmers are major ongoing challenges that are addressed in [Walchhofer, 2024]. The activity and health classifiers are left out for future work.

Pose Estimation, i.e., detecting predefined keypoints of an object, is essential for making reliable predictions. The so-called Animal Pose 10K (AP-10K) keypoint scheme, which comprises 17 keypoints, is exemplarily applied to a cow in Figure 1.2. In this case, the right hip keypoint is not visible and is therefore colored gray.

FIGURE 1.2: Application of the AP-10K keypoint scheme on a cow¹

¹This image has been generated with the help of ChatGPT 4o

For instance, lameness can be detected by tracking leg movement. If the right and left leg keypoints are moving asymmetrically, this is an indicator of lameness. This can only be detected with accurate keypoint predictions. Additionally, concerning the overall pose, movement states such as mounting can be classified to detect heat.

Besides, Re-Identification likely profits from Pose Estimation results. A common problem is that the same cow may look very different depending on the perspective. For instance, the left side of the cow usually has a different coat pattern than the right side. Viewpoint information can be used to overcome this challenge. As Pose Estimation provides information about the viewpoint, the results of this work could be used to improve the Re-Identification of dairy cows by integrating this viewpoint information. By that, the model would have fewer and more reasonable comparisons between the detected cow and images from the database, probably leading to faster and more accurate performance.

There already are autonomous video monitoring systems for dairy cows. One of these systems is called CattleEye, which focuses on detecting different levels of lameness [CattleEye, 2025]. However, this system is designed for large barns with more than 1000 cows on average. Adapting such a system for small-scale farming environments introduces distinct challenges. Smaller barns often have irregular layouts, lower ceilings, and more structural obstructions such as pillars or feed equipment, which can interfere with unobstructed camera views. These constraints can require the use of multiple cameras positioned at varied angles and heights to adequately cover the monitored space. Unlike in larger barns, where standardization allows for consistent camera placement and field of view, the heterogeneity of small barns increases the complexity of video analysis. In particular, issues like occlusion and inconsistent viewpoints become more pronounced. As a result, existing models trained on standardized environments may perform poorly in these settings. To address this domain shift, it becomes necessary to adapt the models through fine-tuning on a representative, custom dataset that reflects the specific spatial and visual conditions found in smaller barns.

1.2 Objectives

Based on the application, several requirements for a Pose Estimation model tailored for small dairy farms can be derived. A list of the requirements can be found in Table 1.1.

Even in small barns, the Pose Estimation model has to be capable of handling multiple objects (**R1**). As action recognition requires instant feedback on each frame of the video, the poses have to be estimated in real-time [Jiang et al., 2023] (**R2**). Despite the speed requirement, the predictions should be as accurate as possible, i.e., the Mean Average Precision (mAP) score (see Section 2.2.2) is to be maximized (**R3**).

ID	Requirement
R1	Multi-object handling
R2	Real-time compatibility
R3	High accuracy
R4	Generalizability
R5	Cost-efficiency
R6	Extensibility

TABLE 1.1: List of requirements

As the model is to be applied at different barns having different camera angles and lighting conditions, it is important that the Pose Estimator learns to generalize well beyond specific settings (**R4**). This is particularly important when the system is rolled out at new barns that the model has not seen during training at all. This is challenging as the custom dataset will be limited in size due to a time-consuming labeling process (see Section 4.1). Fine-tuning on public datasets and using image data augmentation (see Section 2.4) is essential to achieve a cost-efficient solution (**R5**). Due to the limited scope of this work, only a selection of models and datasets can be considered. Hence, it is important that the modeling approaches are extensible for training additional models and using additional datasets (**R6**).

This work aims to compare different Pose Estimation models and their ability to generalize beyond specific settings. First, Real-Time Multi-Person Pose Estimation (RTMPose) [Jiang et al., 2023] is selected due to high inference speed and a reasonably high accuracy reported on animal Pose Estimation tasks. Second, fine-tuning a Real-Time Multi-Person One-Stage Pose Estimation (RTMO) model [Lu et al., 2024] seems promising as it outperformed RTMPose in the human domain. It is to be evaluated whether this model also works for animals as no results have been published in this domain so far. Third, even though this model is not real-time capable and therefore does not meet the previously defined requirements (see **R2**), a Vision Transformer Pose Estimation (ViTPose) model [Xu et al., 2023] is to be trained. This serves as a reference as it achieves state-of-the-art performance in the animal domain, which is why this model is expected to work best also in the domain of small-scale dairy farms. Other models have not been considered as they either do not meet the requirement of real-time capability or perform poorly in terms of accuracy. All models must be trained on the same datasets in order to ensure comparability.

As the setting at small dairy farms is different from publicly available animal datasets, for instance, in terms of perspective and lighting conditions, there is a gap between public animal Pose Estimation datasets and the actual target data. To address this domain gap, a custom dataset is to be annotated and used for training and evaluation.

However, as this is a time-consuming process, the custom dataset will be rather small, which is why the additional use of public datasets is crucial. Four training

approaches that explore different levels of adaptation to the target domain are discussed in this thesis (see Figure 4.7 for a detailed overview):

1. **Baseline:** A model trained on the publicly available datasets is evaluated directly on the domain-specific test set without any exposure to the custom dataset during training.
2. **Fine-tuning:** The pre-trained model is fine-tuned using only the custom dataset (see Section 4.1) to adapt it to the target domain.
3. **Extended pre-training:** The model is additionally pre-trained on AP-10K (a large-scale animal pose dataset, for details see Section 3.1) before fine-tuning. This aims to enhance general animal pose understanding prior to adaptation.
4. **Joint-training:** To prevent forgetting during fine-tuning, the model is trained simultaneously on both the custom dataset and a subset of the AP-10K dataset, ensuring that knowledge from the broader pre-training domain is preserved.

For each of these strategies, in-domain evaluation results are reported. Here, in-domain refers to evaluating the model on images from the same barns that were used for training. In contrast, out-of-domain models are evaluated on barns that have not been seen during training.

The thesis does not cover any background from behavioral biology, such as which keypoint scheme to use and how to draw conclusions from specific poses. For simplicity, the widely established AP-10K keypoint scheme is used throughout this thesis.

The described objectives give rise to the following research questions:

1. How do public and custom datasets impact the performance of Pose Estimation models, particularly in domain-specific tasks?
2. Are the Pose Estimation models able to generalize beyond specific environments, i.e., is the out-of-domain trend approaching the in-domain trend?
3. How well does RTMO perform on non-human keypoint detection? No results on animal data have been published yet.

1.3 Structure

To compare different Pose Estimation models, Chapter 2 presents the theoretical background required for this thesis. First, neural network basics are provided with the focus on the two architectures that have been established in Computer Vision: Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Vision Transformers (ViTs). As none of the models in this thesis are trained from scratch, fine-tuning Machine Learning (ML) models is discussed thereafter. Based on that, a high-level overview of Object

Detection and Pose Estimation, including evaluation metrics, is provided. While Object Detection is not the focus of this work, it is still required for all Top-Down Pose Estimation models as these work based on cropped objects rather than predicting keypoints for the entire image (see Section 2.2). Besides, as common for Computer Vision models, image data augmentation is used in this work and therefore introduced in Section 2.4.

To present the state of the art on Pose Estimation, Chapter 3 is broken down into public Pose Estimation datasets for Animal Pose Estimation and established Pose Estimation models. When it comes to the models, the real-time capable models RTMPose and RTMO as well as the state-of-the-art model ViTPose are presented in detail.

The methodology used to train a pose estimator for dairy cows is presented in Chapter 4. This includes an overview of the custom dataset collected from small-scale barns, as well as the four distinct training approaches discussed in the previous section.

To not only compare the in-domain performance of the different models and training approaches, Chapter 5 additionally presents the result of a domain gap experiment quantifying the out-of-domain performance. Besides, the inference time of the trained models is compared to get an idea of which models would be suitable in a productive system. The chapter concludes by checking the results against the requirements. In Chapter 6, the thesis is completed by providing a summary and an outlook on steps for further improvement.

2 Theoretical Background

To succeed in training a Pose Estimation model for dairy cows, a theoretical background in Computer Vision is required. Being the most established architectures for Computer Vision models, Convolutional Neural Networks and Vision Transformers are introduced in Section 2.1.1 and 2.1.2. As fundamental for training models efficiently, Section 2.1.3 discusses theoretical background about fine-tuning ML models. As all Top-Down Pose Estimation models require Object Detection, an overview about the task, state-of-the-art models and evaluation metrics is given in Section 2.2. The next section provides a high-level overview of the key concepts in Pose Estimation as well as evaluation metrics. A more detailed overview of the state of the art on Pose Estimation can be found in Chapter 3. To boost the performance, image data is usually augmented during training, which is explained in Section 2.4.

2.1 Neural Network Architectures for Computer Vision

Modern object detectors and pose estimators rely on neural network architectures. For image data, Convolutional Neural Networks have been state of the art for years [Raghu et al., 2022]. The introduction of Vision Transformers [Dosovitskiy et al., 2021] offered an alternative to this approach. This chapter provides details on both architectures and evaluates their strengths and weaknesses.

Both architectures fall under the category of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). Inspired by the human brain, an ANN consists of connected neurons that fire if a certain threshold is reached. The structure of a basic ANN is outlined in Figure 2.1. This architecture is referred to as a Multi Layer Perceptron (MLP).

Every neural network consists of one input layer, an arbitrary number of hidden layers, and one output layer. The number of neurons per layer can be fully customized. In this case, each layer is fully connected, meaning that every neuron in a given layer is connected to every neuron in the next layer. [Frochte, 2018]

A neuron consists of inputs, weights, and an activation function, as exemplified for the first hidden neuron in Figure 2.1. The activation value a is computed by applying a nonlinear function func to the weighted sum of its inputs. To incorporate the bias term, a constant pseudo-input $x_0 = 1$ is typically added to the input vector, and the corresponding weight w_{10} serves as the learnable bias. This results in the following formulation: [Frochte, 2018]

FIGURE 2.1: Architecture outline of a MLP

$$a_{11}(w, x) = \text{func} \left(\sum_{i=0}^n w_{1i} x_i \right) \quad (2.1)$$

Importantly, the activation function must be non-linear to enable the network to learn complex representations. Using a purely linear activation would make the entire network equivalent to a single linear transformation. Three non-linear activation functions are visualized in Figure 2.2. [Frochte, 2018]

FIGURE 2.2: Visualization of three non-linear activation functions

A natural but overly simplistic choice for an activation function is the Heaviside step function, which outputs either 0 or 1 depending on the input. However, this function is not suitable for training neural networks because its gradient vanishes almost everywhere and is undefined at the step, making gradient-based optimization infeasible. [Frochte, 2018]

To address this, differentiable functions with non-zero gradients over a broader range are used instead. A common choice is the logistic sigmoid function, which smoothly maps real-valued inputs to outputs between 0 and 1 and allows gradual activation depending on the input and the neuron's weights. The logistic sigmoid function is defined as: [Frochte, 2018]

$$\text{sig}(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (2.2)$$

Another common choice for func (see Equation 2.1) is the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU). The ReLU function replaces all negative pixel values by zero: [Karn, 2016]

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (2.3)$$

To obtain class probabilities in the output layer, a softmax function is usually applied as the activation function func (see Equation 2.1) at the end of the network. This converts the raw output logits into a probability distribution over classes, making the outputs interpretable as class probabilities. The softmax function for a vector $\mathbf{z} = [z_1, z_2, \dots, z_K] \in \mathbb{R}^K$ is defined as:

$$\text{softmax}(z_i) = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{z_j}}, \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, K \quad (2.4)$$

This ensures that each output $\text{softmax}(z_i) \in (0, 1)$, and that the sum over all classes is 1: $\sum_{i=1}^K \text{softmax}(z_i) = 1$. [Phillips, 2023]

In Computer Vision tasks, an image can be represented as a matrix of pixel values, which usually serves as the input of the network. In case of RGB images, the input consists of three 2D pixel matrices, one for each color channel. In image classification, the output layer contains one neuron for each class, and the output value of each neuron can be interpreted as the predicted probability for that class. The hidden layers differ depending on the network architecture. Details are provided in the following two subsections.

2.1.1 Convolutional Neural Networks

Similar to a basic neural network, a CNN consists of an input layer, several hidden layers and an output layer. The architecture of a CNN used for object classification is shown in Figure 2.3.

FIGURE 2.3: Architecture outline of a CNN [MathWorks, 2025]

As the name suggests, the convolution operation is a central component of CNNs. The key idea is to apply a filter matrix, often referred to as a kernel, across different spatial regions of the input image to detect local features such as edges, gradients, or textures. This is achieved by sliding the same kernel across the image and computing the element-wise product between the kernel and the overlapping region of the input, followed by summation. The resulting values form the so-called feature map. Because the same kernel is applied across all locations, this operation enables the detection of specific patterns regardless of their position. This property is known as translation invariance and is achieved through weight sharing. Figure 2.4 illustrates this process using a Laplace kernel applied to a sample pixel matrix. [Karn, 2016]

FIGURE 2.4: Visualization of the convolution operation

In classical image processing, fixed kernels such as the Laplace kernel are applied to detect specific features like edges or intensity gradients, independent of orientation. The Laplace kernel, for example, highlights regions of rapid brightness change and can vary in size and form. [Burger and Burge, 2016]

In contrast, CNNs typically learn the appropriate kernels directly from data during training, rather than relying on predefined filters. Each learned kernel extracts a

specific type of feature from the input and gives rise to one feature map, also referred to as a feature channel. These feature channels are analogous to color channels (e.g., RGB) in the input image, but unlike the fixed number of input channels, CNNs can learn and use hundreds of feature channels per layer. The increasing depth of the cuboids in the Feature Learning section of Figure 2.3 illustrates the growing number of such feature channels throughout the network.

As most real-world problems are non-linear and the convolution operation is linear, a non-linear operation such as the ReLU (see Section 2.1) is added after every convolution operation.

To reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature map, the stride parameter can be increased. The stride defines the number of pixels by which the convolutional or pooling kernel is shifted between two successive positions. For example, instead of using a stride of 1 (as shown in Figure 2.4), setting the stride to 2 means the kernel is placed every second pixel, effectively downsampling the output. The effect of a stride of 2 is illustrated in Figure 2.5. [Stanford University, 2025]

Figure 2.3 emphasizes that information is condensed with each pooling iteration. The underlying idea is to prioritize the presence of features over their exact spatial location. Pooling is a downsampling operation that aggregates the values of a $n \times n$ neighborhood. Common choices for aggregation are taking the maximum or average of these values. In particular, max pooling preserves the most prominent activation within a region, which highlights the strongest feature response while reducing spatial precision. This trade-off helps the network generalize better by focusing on whether a feature is present rather than where it occurs precisely. Figure 2.5 illustrates a maximum pooling using a 2×2 neighborhood and stride 2. [Stanford University, 2025]

FIGURE 2.5: Visualization of the pooling operation

At the end of the network, a classification is to be done (see Figure 2.3). The 3D feature representations are flattened into a 1D array, followed by a fully connected layer similar to what is done in a basic neural network (see Figure 2.1).

In CNNs, the concept of the receptive field helps to understand their locality. For any given output neuron, its receptive field refers to the set of input neurons (here: color values of pixels of the input image) that influence its activation. Due to the stacking of multiple convolutional and pooling layers, the receptive field typically increases with network depth. However, in practice, CNNs are often not deep enough for

neurons in earlier layers, or even in the final convolutional layer, to cover the entire input image. As a result, the feature maps before the flattening step primarily capture local features. [Adaloglou, 2020]

These local features, however, are passed to one or more fully connected layers after flattening. In these layers, each neuron receives input from all activations in the previous layer. Thus, while individual convolutional neurons only respond to local regions, the final classification decision is made based on a combination of all extracted local features, effectively allowing the output neurons to incorporate information from the entire input image. In this sense, CNNs first extract localized patterns and then integrate them globally to make a final decision.

2.1.2 Vision Transformers

Transformers became famous for Natural Language Processing. Large Language Models such as ChatGPT are based on the ideas of [Vaswani et al., 2017], which are introduced in the following.

A transformer generally aims to transform some input sequence into an output sequence. For instance, in machine translation, the task might be to translate an English sentence (input) to German (output). To do so, transformers use an encoder-decoder structure. The encoder converts the input sentence into a sequence of numerical vectors that capture the meaning and relationships between words. These are called embeddings. The decoder generates the output based on these embeddings. [Alammar and Grootendorst, 2024]

Intuitively, the embeddings can be described as vectors in a high-dimensional space. The idea is that the directions and distances between different vectors in that space align with their corresponding semantic meaning. For example, the vectors for king and queen should point in a similar direction as both refer to the head of a monarchy. Besides, the distance between these two vectors should be similar to the distance between the embeddings for man and woman, as both distances semantically describe a change in gender. [Alammar and Grootendorst, 2024]

Inspired by other Deep Learning approaches, stacking multiple encoder and decoder blocks helps to increase the model's capacity. For instance, in [Vaswani et al., 2017], six identical encoders are stacked on top of each other, followed by six identical decoders. This increased depth enables the model to tackle more complex tasks than a single block could handle.

Instead of relying on convolutions, [Vaswani et al., 2017] proposes an approach that is solely based on a so-called self-attention mechanism. A word can have several meanings depending on the context it is used in. The idea of self-attention is that for each word, it is necessary to learn how much attention it should pay to the other words in order to understand its meaning.

Mathematically, a static embedding matrix $X \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$ contains all N words of the document embedded into the D -dimensional embedding space. This matrix can be thought of as a lookup table for the embedding of each word that results from some pre-training. However, depending on the specific context, the pre-trained embedding is to be updated.

Self-attention aims to transform such a static embedding matrix into a contextual embedding matrix. The static embedding matrix X is projected into **Query** ($Q = XW_Q \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$), **Key** ($K = XW_K \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$) and **Value** ($V = XW_V \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$) matrices through learnable weight matrices $W_Q \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$, $W_K \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$ and $W_V \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$. The idea is that when taking the dot product between the Query and the Key matrix ($QK^T \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$), we can capture the similarity between the embeddings: For vectors pointing in a similar direction in the embedding space, the dot product produces a large value. To normalize these values, a softmax can be applied. The normalized values can be interpreted as attention weights ranging from 0 to 1. These are used to update the Value matrix V , weighting each word embedding according to how much attention is to be paid to all other words. As the softmax is sensitive to large ranges, normalizing by the square root of D before computing the softmax improves numerical stability. The described process is formalized in the scaled dot-product attention formula: [Vaswani et al., 2017]

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{D}} \right) V \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D} \quad (2.5)$$

There are many different ways that context can influence the meaning of a word. For example, attention could mean looking for either preceding adjectives or nouns in the same sentence. To model these, Vision Transformers in practice run several self-attention heads in parallel, which is known as multi-head self-attention. Each head has its own weight matrices for Q , K and V . This enables the network to capture diverse types of contextual relationships, typically resulting in more informative features. Analogously to CNNs, this is similar to using multiple kernels, each learning different features. [Vaswani et al., 2017]

Facing Computer Vision tasks such as image classification, [Dosovitskiy et al., 2021] came up with the idea to treat image patches as words. An image patch can be defined as a small, fixed-size matrix of pixels extracted from the image. Unlike a kernel placement in CNNs, which is a region of the image weighted by a learnable filter (see Section 2.1.1), a patch in Vision Transformers is simply a fixed segment of the image itself. The architecture of their proposed ViT model is shown in Figure 2.6.

While the original Transformer architecture consists of both an encoder and a decoder, the Vision Transformer uses only the encoder [Dosovitskiy et al., 2021]. This design choice aligns with its purpose: image classification. In this setting, a decoder

FIGURE 2.6: Architecture outline of a ViT [Dosovitskiy et al., 2021]

is unnecessary, as a simple MLP head (see Section 2.1) atop the encoder suffices. [Alammar and Grootendorst, 2024]

To encode the image, it is divided into patches of equal size, e.g. $3 * 3 = 9$ patches as in Figure 2.6. The multi-dimensional pixel vector is flattened to a single dimension in order to use the existing transformer architecture, which is designed for 1D-sequences. The resulting loss of explicit spatial information is tackled in other papers such as [Ho et al., 2019], where axial attention, i.e., attention along each single axis, is applied.

The flattened patch vector is transformed into a D -dimensional embedding space by feeding it through a fully connected layer. To retain spatial information without using convolutions, positional encoding is added to each patch embedding. By that, each embedding holds information about the pixels in the patch as well as where this patch is located in the image. [Dosovitskiy et al., 2021]

Having obtained patch embeddings, the self-attention mechanism is applied. The idea is the same as when dealing with language: The aim is to learn, for each patch, which other patches it should pay attention to in order to understand its meaning. For example, in an image of a cow in a grassland, the patch containing the cow's head should attend more strongly to patches containing other parts of the cow, while paying little attention to background patches such as the grass.

At the end of each encoder block, the embeddings are passed to an MLP to further enrich the representations by adding complexity and allowing for non-linear relations. To stabilize and speed up training, Layer Normalization is applied which ensures that the input to each layer has a normalized mean and variance [Ba, Kiros, and Hinton, 2016]. [Xu et al., 2023]

Thanks to the attention mechanism, Vision Transformers are able to model global relationships between patches at every layer. For instance, the attention mechanism can learn that the bottom left and top right corners should be considered together. However, this global perspective operates at the patch level, not the pixel level. As a result, the extent to which the model captures fine-grained, global information depends heavily on the patch size: the smaller the patches, the more detailed and globally-aware the model's understanding becomes. However, reducing the patch size leads to more patches and thus causes high computational costs.

2.1.3 Fine-Tuning of Machine Learning Models

In practice, Computer Vision models are rarely trained from scratch. Instead, model checkpoints of a model trained on other datasets are used for weight initialization. It is common practice to use the ImageNet dataset for pre-training the backbone, which contains a wide variety of object categories [Deng et al., 2009]. Intuitively, the resulting weights provide a better starting point for the actual task than random initialization. Based on this checkpoint, the actual target dataset is used to train the final model. This process is called fine-tuning.

The first question that naturally arises is why training on different datasets than the target dataset is beneficial for the model's performance on the target dataset. Intuitively, different tasks often share common features. For instance, taking CNNs as an example, it turns out that regardless of the Computer Vision task these networks have been trained on, the first layers tend to extract basic features such as edges of different orientations or simple shapes such as circles. These general-purpose features are often transferable across tasks. [Yosinski et al., 2014]

From the theoretical Machine Learning perspective, [Baxter, 1995] provides proofs why internal representations must be learned from multiple comparable tasks in order to generalize well. This is what [Bengio et al., 2011] shows empirically: Model performance benefits from out-of-distribution examples, that is, examples that come from a slightly different distribution than the target distribution. For instance, a model that is to be trained for small-scale dairy farms might profit from large-scale farm data or even from data that contains different, but similar animals. The intuition behind this is that training on varied or slightly mismatched data forces the model to learn more abstract and general features, rather than overfitting to a narrow dataset. As a result, the learned representations are more robust and transferable. [Bengio et al., 2011]

When fine-tuning models, it may sometimes be beneficial to freeze the first few layers that extract task-agnostic features such as edges. This helps to avoid overfitting, particularly when working with small datasets and large models. Freezing early layers prevents the model from unnecessarily adjusting low-level, general-purpose

features that are already suitable for many vision tasks. Instead, only the higher layers are fine-tuned to adapt to task-specific patterns, reducing the risk of overfitting to the noise or limited diversity of the new dataset. Again, the assumption is that in these first layers, basic features are extracted that are similar in both domains. This phenomenon is often referred to as Transfer Learning as the original distribution differs from the actual target distribution but there are common features that are transferable between the different problems. [Yosinski et al., 2014]

While the publications on ViTPose and RTMPose explicitly state that their backbones were pre-trained on ImageNet [Xu et al., 2023, Jiang et al., 2023], the authors of RTMO do not mention this detail [Lu et al., 2024]. Nevertheless, given the prevalence of ImageNet pre-training, it is reasonable to assume that RTMO employs a similar strategy, facilitating a fair comparison of these three models in Chapters 4 and 5.

2.2 Object Detection

2.2.1 Overview

When applying Top-Down Pose Estimation, Object Detection results are required to first localize each individual in the image (see Section 2.3). An object detector aims to locate instances of specified object classes by predicting bounding boxes and associated class probabilities. Given an input image, for example showing multiple cows in a barn, the object detector outputs a list of bounding boxes (typically represented by x and y coordinates of the top left-hand corner and the width and height of the box) and confidence scores indicating the model's belief that the bounding box is accurately identified and located. This score is calculated by multiplying the class probability (softmax output at the end of the network, see Equation 2.4) with the Intersection over Union (IoU) (see Section 2.2.2). [Redmon et al., 2016]

Object Detection is a field of active research that has gained significant attention due to its wide applicability in areas like autonomous driving, video surveillance, and animal monitoring. Traditional feature-based methods, such as using fixed kernels to extract specific information, have been taken over from Deep Learning approaches such as CNNs that learn these kernels (see Section 2.1.1), achieving impressive results despite the high complexity of the task. [Zou et al., 2023]

The first milestone after traditional detectors using hand-crafted features was CNN-based two-stage models. CNNs have been established in Computer Vision due to their ability to condense pixel information into high-level features such as shapes or objects (see Section 2.1.1). The first two-stage detector that was introduced is the Regions with CNN features (R-CNN) model Girshick et al., 2014. In the first stage, the model generates a set of region proposals, that is, suggested bounding boxes that may contain objects. In the second stage, each proposed region is classified, meaning the model predicts which object class (e.g., cow, dog, or person) is present

in the region. Proposals with low confidence are discarded by applying a confidence filter. R-CNN suffers from slow inference due to redundant computations: CNN feature extraction is performed separately for each region proposal, even though many proposals overlap and share large parts of the image content. [Zou et al., 2023]

To increase inference speed for applications with real-time requirements (such as in this work), one-stage detectors were introduced by [Redmon et al., 2016]. With the You Only Look Once (YOLO) architecture, this approach achieves significantly faster performance compared to two-stage detectors, as the entire image is processed by a single neural network in one pass. Instead of using a separate second-stage classification step, Object Detection is framed as a unified regression problem that includes both localization and classification. The image is divided into a grid, and for each cell, the network predicts bounding boxes, associated confidence scores, and class probabilities. [Redmon et al., 2016]

While the reduced number of processing stages contributes to the improved inference speed, it is not the only factor. One-stage detectors generally simplify the architecture and avoid per-region feature extraction and redundant computations typical in two-stage pipelines. However, this speedup may come at the cost of reduced localization precision, particularly for small or densely packed objects, due to the fixed grid resolution used for prediction.

This one-stage paradigm has inspired numerous successors to the original YOLO model, as well as other real-time optimized approaches such as Real-Time Models for object DETection (RTMDet) [Lyu et al., 2022]. RTMDet further improves inference speed through architectural enhancements such as efficient backbone designs and advanced augmentation techniques [Lyu et al., 2022]. These approaches allow for a better trade-off between speed and accuracy, enabling deployment in latency-sensitive applications.

Detection Transformer (DETR) [Carion et al., 2020] offers an alternative to the YOLO approach. Instead of using convolutions, the characteristic idea of transformers is to use self-attention. The architecture of Vision Transformers, including the self-attention mechanism, have been introduced in Section 2.1.2.

2.2.2 Evaluation Metrics for Object Detection

To allow for a fair comparison between different models, standardized metrics are required. In Object Detection tasks, it is necessary to first find a metric that quantifies how close the predicted bounding box (B_{pred}) is to the ground truth annotation (B_{gt}). For this purpose, the IoU is commonly used, which compares the overlap between two bounding boxes. Mathematically, the bounding boxes are treated as sets of pixels in the image plane, and the IoU is defined as the ratio of the number of pixels in

the intersection to the number of pixels in the union:[Wood and Chollet, 2022]

$$IoU = \frac{|B_{\text{pred}} \cap B_{\text{gt}}|}{|B_{\text{pred}} \cup B_{\text{gt}}|} \quad (2.6)$$

Consequently, the IoU is between 0 for predictions having no overlap with the ground truth at all and 1 for perfect predictions.

For Computer Vision tasks, evaluation is less straightforward than for standard tasks such as classification. The key question is what to treat as True Positives (TP), False Positives (FP), False Negatives (FN) and True Negatives (TN). These cases are illustrated in Figure 2.7, showing ground truth annotations (gray) and exemplary predictions (green and red) of a dairy cow object detector.

FIGURE 2.7: Visualization of how object detections are evaluated

For evaluation, the IoU scores for all predictions with all ground truth bounding boxes are computed. A prediction is a True Positive candidate if two things hold:

1. The predicted bounding box has an IoU above a predefined threshold (e.g. $IoU > 0.5$) for at least one ground truth bounding box and
2. The predicted class matches the class of the ground truth annotation (in this case, the class of the annotations is "Cow").

Each ground truth bounding box is then matched to at most one prediction, and that is the prediction with the highest IoU (and the same class ID). This prediction is considered a **True Positive**. The greater the IoU threshold is chosen, the harder it is to make correct predictions. [Wood and Chollet, 2022]

After the matching process, remaining predictions are treated as **False Positives** as they either have a suboptimal IoU with the associated ground truth (see top right hand corner: an additional object is detected) or the class prediction is wrong (see bottom right hand corner: a dog has been detected as a cow). If an object is not detected at all, this is a **False Negative** (see top left-hand corner: the cow is not detected by the model). [Wood and Chollet, 2022]

In contrast, the concept of a **True Negative**, i.e., cases where no object is predicted and none is actually present, is not well-defined in Object Detection. The reason is that the number of possible bounding boxes that could be drawn in an image is practically infinite, making an exhaustive definition of True Negatives neither feasible nor meaningful. As a result, evaluation metrics that rely on True Negatives, such as Accuracy or the True Negative Rate, are not suitable for Object Detection tasks. Fortunately, commonly used metrics like Precision and Recall avoid this issue, as they are defined purely in terms of True Positives, False Positives, and False Negatives. [Wood and Chollet, 2022]

The metrics previously described can be summarized in a so-called confusion matrix (see Table 2.1).

	Predicted Positive	Predicted Negative
Actual Positive (P)	True Positives (TP)	False Negatives (FN)
Actual Negative (N)	False Positives (FP)	True Negatives (TN)

TABLE 2.1: Confusion matrix

Precision and Recall are essential metrics for evaluation. Precision is defined as the fraction of correctly predicted positive cases out of all cases predicted as positive: [Manning, Raghavan, and Schütze, 2008]

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2.7)$$

Recall, in contrast, relates the correctly predicted positive cases to the actual positive cases: [Manning, Raghavan, and Schütze, 2008]

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} = \frac{TP}{P} \quad (2.8)$$

Consider a trivial model predicting everything as positive. This model has a perfect Recall score of 1 as by predicting positive values only, there cannot be any False Negatives. However, assuming a balanced class distribution, the Precision of this model is very low due to many False Positives. Consider another model that is very conservative and only predicts a positive value when it is very certain. This model achieves a high Precision score by minimizing the number of False Positives, but the Recall score suffers from many False Negatives. These two examples illustrate that there is a trade-off between these two metrics: An increase in one usually results in a decrease of the other.

To filter out low-confidence predictions, a confidence threshold is usually applied. For example, setting this threshold to 0.5 means that all predicted bounding boxes with a confidence score below 0.5 are discarded and not evaluated. This threshold has a direct impact on Precision and Recall:

- A higher threshold tends to increase Precision, since only the most confident predictions are kept, reducing the number of False Positives. However, this can also decrease Recall, as some True Positives may be filtered out along with low-confidence predictions.
- Conversely, a lower threshold typically increases Recall, because more predictions, including potentially correct ones with low confidence, are retained. But this often comes at the cost of lower Precision, as more False Positives are included.

To take into account both Precision and Recall for all bounding box predictions, the Average Precision (AP) defined as the area under the Precision-Recall curve can be used. This curve can be obtained by plotting Precision on the x-axis and Recall on the y-axis for all possible confidence thresholds. The sample data of a binary classification problem in Table 2.2 is used to illustrate such a curve in Figure 2.8. [Manning, Raghavan, and Schütze, 2008]

Confidence ↓	Class	TP	FP	FN	Precision	Recall
0.95	1	1	0	5-1=4	$\frac{1}{1+0} = 1$	$\frac{1}{1+4} = 0.2$
0.87	1	2	0	3	1.00	0.4
0.81	0	2	1	3	0.67	0.4
0.72	1	3	1	2	0.75	0.6
0.64	1	4	1	1	0.80	0.8
0.53	0	4	2	1	0.67	0.8
0.46	0	4	3	1	0.57	0.8
0.37	1	5	3	0	0.63	1.0
0.33	0	5	4	0	0.56	1.0
0.29	0	5	5	0	0.50	1.0

TABLE 2.2: Sample data for a Precision-Recall curve

FIGURE 2.8: Precision-Recall curve of a sample model

Each row in Table 2.2 represents a positive prediction, i.e., the model predicts 1 with a certain confidence. If the class is truly 1, the number of True Positives is increased and the number of False Negatives is decreased by 1. If it is actually 0, this prediction is a False Positive. By using the formulas from above, Precision and Recall can be computed for each prediction. This simulates the effect of choosing different confidence thresholds. The plot shows the Precision-Recall curve for this data in blue. The model achieves an AP score of 0.82 which equals the Area Under Curve (AUC). A perfect model would always predict 1 for actual positives and therefore has an AP of 1 (green line). The expected curve of a random model is pictured in red.

As the AP value depends on the defined IoU threshold, it makes sense to average multiple AP values for multiple IoU thresholds. This is known as the mAP. The standard Common Objects in COntext (COCO) mAP score for n classes is defined as

$$\text{mAP} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{|T|} \sum_{t \in T} AP_k@t \quad (2.9)$$

where $AP_k@t$ denotes the Average Precision for keypoint k at IoU threshold t , and T is the set of thresholds defined as:

$$T = \{ t \in (0, 1) \mid \exists k \in \mathbb{N}_0 : t = 0.5 + 0.05 \cdot k \}$$

This corresponds to the standard COCO evaluation metric, which averages the AP scores over 10 IoU thresholds ranging from 0.50 to 0.95 in increments of 0.05. [Wood and Chollet, 2022]

2.3 Pose Estimation Overview

2.3.1 Key Concepts: Top-Down and Bottom-Up

Pose Estimation refers to "identifying the category and location of a series of body keypoints" [Yu et al., 2021]. There are two main approaches to estimating poses: Top-Down and Bottom-Up. These are visualized in Figure 2.9.

FIGURE 2.9: Top-Down vs. Bottom-Up approach for Pose Estimation [Liu, Qiu, and Zhang, 2024]

The Top-Down approach is divided into two stages. In the first stage, objects have to be detected, usually using an additional Object Detection model. These detections are then fed into the second stage of the model. Within each detected bounding box, which is often padded by a certain percentage to allow for some tolerance in detection, the keypoints of the detected object are estimated. Exemplary Top-Down models are ViTPose and RTMPose which are extensively described in the sections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2. [Liu, Qiu, and Zhang, 2024]

In contrast, Bottom-Up models estimate the keypoints of all objects simultaneously, without relying on Object Detection in advance. After detecting all keypoints in the image, the model must group them into sets that correspond to individual object instances. This keypoint association step is typically achieved using spatial grouping strategies such as clustering algorithms. This process can be challenging, especially in crowded scenes or when keypoints from different objects are close together. Hence, Bottom-Up methods are not further considered in this thesis. [Liu, Qiu, and Zhang, 2024]

The RTMO model described in Section 3.2.3 introduces another category: The one-stage approaches. Similar to the YOLO paradigm in Object Detection (see Section 2.2.1), RTMO simultaneously detects both bounding boxes and keypoints in a single unified network pass. This contrasts with two-stage models, where Object Detection and Keypoint Estimation are performed sequentially, often by separate components. The one-stage design eliminates intermediate steps such as region proposal generation or per-instance cropping and processing, thereby reducing overall computational overhead. As a result, inference time is significantly improved without requiring separate passes for Object Detection and Pose Estimation. [Lu et al., 2024]

2.3.2 Prediction Paradigms for 2D Pose Estimation

Different Pose Estimation models follow different paradigms to predict keypoint coordinates. First of all, there are two ways of handling a two-dimensional image:

1. preserving spatial context by making 2D predictions or
2. assuming independence of x- and y-direction and thus making two independent 1D predictions (one along each direction).

Assuming independence has two main effects. First, this approach is faster as its complexity scales linearly instead of quadratically with the image dimension. However, the assumption is mathematically incorrect and may cause inaccurate predictions. These effects are further evaluated in Section 3.2.2.

Another distinction can be made based on which degree of sub-pixel accuracy is to be achieved. Sub-pixel accuracy refers to the fact that when predicting keypoints, it is usually not sufficient to predict the pixel that contains this keypoint, but it is desired to get the exact location within this pixel. This becomes especially important

when high-resolution images are downsampled to the network's input size. One pixel in the model's space may correspond to many pixels in the original image, so fractional predictions are required to maintain high spatial accuracy after rescaling.

The question that naturally arises is how to achieve sub-pixel accuracy when each pixel is composed of a single value. The solution is to take into account the neighborhood of each pixel. Figure 2.10 illustrates this idea.

255	255	255	255
255	255	255	255
197	197	197	197
0	0	0	0

FIGURE 2.10: Visualization of sub-pixel accuracy

Imagine a white wall with a continuous horizontal black bar at the bottom of the wall as shown in Figure 2.10. While the real wall is continuous, a picture of this wall is composed of discrete pixels ranging from 0 to 255 (colored in green). The upper part of the 4x4 pixel matrix contains only 255 entries, encoding the white color of the wall. The lower black part of the matrix is composed of 0 entries only. As the edge between the white and the black part of the wall is unlikely to be exactly between two pixel rows, there will be one row of pixels encoding a gray value, as this region contains both black and white elements of the wall. This gray value provides information about the location of the edge within the pixel. In this case, as its value of 197 is closer to white than to black, this pixel contains a higher proportion of the white part of the wall. This implies that the edge is close to the black part (of which only a small fraction is present in this pixel), i.e., further down in the pixel.

Two approaches for different levels of sub-pixel accuracy have been established: Heatmap-based regression of continuous pixels (1) and coordinate classification using bins instead of a continuous scale (2). Figure 2.11 visualizes these approaches.

FIGURE 2.11: Visualization of keypoint regression vs. classification

Figure 2.11 shows a 3x3 pixel grid (black), each pixel being divided into 2 bins along each axis (green) and a ground truth keypoint coordinate (red). While regression approaches aim to regress this exact coordinate, classification aims to predict the correct bin only. Note that both approaches can be modeled either by making 2D or independent 1D predictions as described above. [Li et al., 2022]

2.3.3 Evaluation Metrics for Pose Estimation

To apply the mAP metric in analogy to Object Detection (see Section 2.2.2), an analog to the IoU metric is required that is designed to measure keypoint instead of bounding box similarity. Therefore, [Lin et al., 2014] introduced the Object Keypoint Similarity (OKS):

$$\text{OKS} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K \exp\left(-\frac{d_i^2}{2s^2\kappa_i^2}\right) \delta(v_i > 0)}{\sum_{i=1}^K \delta(v_i > 0)} \quad (2.10)$$

It is iterated over K keypoints, where the number of keypoints is defined by the underlying keypoint scheme (e.g., AP-10K uses $K = 17$). The Euclidean distance between the predicted and ground truth keypoint is denoted as d_i , where smaller values indicate better alignment. To normalize for object size, the term s represents the scale of the object and can be derived from the area of the object's bounding box. This ensures that predictions for large objects are not overly penalized compared to smaller ones. [Lin et al., 2014]

To allow for varying precision expectations across different keypoints, a constant κ_i is introduced for each keypoint i . This tolerance parameter adjusts how strict the scoring is for that keypoint: a higher κ_i value results in greater tolerance, meaning larger distances d_i still receive relatively high scores. This is motivated by two reasons: First, certain keypoints such as eyes require higher localization precision than others like shoulders or hips, due to their smaller size and visual distinctiveness. Second, some keypoints (e.g., the neck) may inherently suffer from annotation ambiguity, making high-precision localization less meaningful. [Lin et al., 2014]

The visibility flag $\delta(v_i > 0)$ ensures that occluded or unannotated keypoints do not affect the score. Here, v_i is the visibility label for keypoint i , taken from the ground truth. It is typically a discrete value with: 0 = not labeled, 1 = labeled but not visible, and 2 = labeled and visible. The indicator function $\delta(v_i > 0)$ maps this to 1 if the keypoint is labeled (regardless of visibility), and 0 otherwise. This guarantees that only annotated keypoints contribute to the score. Note that in this work, it is not distinguished between visible and non-visible keypoints during labeling, but only visible keypoints have been annotated for simplicity (see Section 4.1). [Lin et al., 2014]

Additionally, exponential weighting is applied, ensuring the score falls between $0 < \frac{1}{e^x} \leq 1 \forall x > 0$, where a value of 1 indicates perfect alignment and everything close

to 0 signifies poor alignment.

A more straightforward metric is the Percentage of Correct Keypoints (PCK). A predicted keypoint is considered correct if its Euclidean distance to the associated ground truth keypoint is at most a predefined fraction of the bounding box diagonal. This threshold is often set to 0.05, i.e., a keypoint is correct if it falls within the distance of 5% of the bounding box diagonal from the true keypoint. In the further course of this thesis, PCK indicates the PCK@0.05. Compared to the OKS-based mAP metric, it does not take into account the differences across keypoints (such as including κ_i as done in Equation 2.10). Therefore, OKS-based mAP is the more established metric and serves as the primary evaluation criterion throughout this thesis. [Andriluka et al., 2014]

The assignment of keypoint detections to ground truth keypoints is similar to the process for Object Detection described in Section 2.2.2. The matching is done separately for each object, i.e., all keypoints within one bounding box are considered. Then, instead of bounding boxes, keypoints are merged based on a keypoint similarity threshold instead of an IoU threshold. The similarity of an individual keypoint has already been introduced as part of Equation 2.10:

$$KS_i = \exp\left(-\frac{d_i^2}{2s^2\kappa_i^2}\right) \quad (2.11)$$

2.4 Image Data Augmentation

Machine Learning models typically benefit from larger volumes of training data. The idea of image data augmentation is to enhance the training dataset by modifying the input images during training. This is especially helpful when dealing with small datasets as it does not incur additional labeling costs. There are many different kinds of image data augmentation. This chapter provides an overview of exemplary augmentation techniques used for training Pose Estimation models for dairy cows.

One common data augmentation technique is to **flip** the image horizontally, vertically, or diagonally. However, it's important to ensure that such transformations do not alter the inherent meaning of the dataset. For instance, in Pose Estimation tasks, keypoints are typically labeled based on their position relative to the object (e.g., right or left knee). When an image is flipped horizontally, these labels must also be appropriately swapped to maintain consistency (see Figure 2.12). Modern libraries like MMPose offer built-in functionality to handle such adjustments automatically. Vertical flipping is not suitable in this context, as cows are unlikely to appear upside down with their legs in the air. [Kumar et al., 2023]

Cropping and resizing is another common technique, using only a part of the image or rescaling it to a fixed size. This helps the model learn to focus on different regions and improves robustness against changes in scale or object location. In pose

FIGURE 2.12: Horizontal image flip with exemplary label swap

estimation, cropping is often guided by bounding boxes, sometimes even focusing on partial body regions such as the upper or lower half. This is known as a Half Body Transform, which is especially helpful to improve the predictions in crowded scenes with many occlusions. [Kumar et al., 2023]

Rotation applies a random angular shift to the input image. This encourages the model to become invariant to changes in the orientation of the subject. For dairy cow datasets, it can simulate different viewpoints, such as a slightly tilted camera or animal posture. Again, in this application, the rotation angle should be constrained to prevent generating unrealistic images of upside-down cows. [Kumar et al., 2023]

Jitter introduces random noise in color properties like hue, saturation, brightness, or contrast. This simulates lighting variations and color distortions that may occur due to environmental changes, helping the model generalize across different recording conditions. [Kumar et al., 2023]

There are more advanced operations such as applying blur and coarse dropout (randomly masking parts of the image). For more details, refer to [Kumar et al., 2023]. In this work, all models have been trained using the basic augmentation techniques described above.

3 State of the Art on Pose Estimation

The limited size of the custom dataset for estimating the pose of dairy cows requires public datasets to reach a sufficiently large training dataset. These are discussed at the beginning of this chapter. In addition, state-of-the-art models with special attention to real-time capability are outlined in Section 3.2.

3.1 Public Datasets for Animal Pose Estimation

The first public dataset for Animal Pose Estimation was the Animal-Pose dataset. This dataset contains nearly 5000 labeled images with over 6000 instances of five different species: cats, dogs, horses, sheep and cows. The proposed keypoint scheme uses 20 keypoints, including paws, knees, hips, tail root, withers, neck, eyes, nose and ears. [Cao et al., 2019]

The AP-10K dataset heavily extended the diversity of included animal species. As the name suggests, it includes about 10 thousand annotated images of 54 species. All annotations follow a newly introduced keypoint scheme that includes 17 different keypoints. In comparison to Animal-Pose, neither the ears nor the withers keypoints are used in the AP-10K keypoint scheme. Animal Pose Estimation and Tracking 36K (APT-36K) [Yang et al., 2022] and its successor Animal Pose Estimation and Tracking Version 2 (APTv2) [Yang et al., 2023] are extensions of the AP-10K dataset which includes more species as well as multi-frame data for tracking. A glance at images included in AP-10K can be found in Figure 3.1. [Yu et al., 2021]

Upon examining these images, the domain gap between AP-10K and images of dairy cows becomes apparent. Focusing on mammals, AP-10K mainly includes quadruped animals such as cows, except for different species of monkeys and bats. However, the keypoints of a squirrel have significantly different visual characteristics than those of a cow.

For an extensive analysis of animal behavior, [Ng et al., 2022] suggests Animal Kingdom, a large-scale dataset with 850 different species. For Pose Estimation, this dataset contains more than 30 thousand images. The keypoint scheme is extended by additional tail and torso keypoints in comparison to Animal-Pose and AP-10K.

FIGURE 3.1: Exemplary images of the AP-10K dataset [Yu et al., 2021]

Beyond poses, the actions of the animals have been recorded in various scenes and weather conditions. [Ng et al., 2022]

[Banik, Li, and Dong, 2021] introduced Animals with Attributes (AwA) Pose, a Pose Estimation dataset specific for quadruped animals. The number of annotated images is similar to AP-10K. However, the keypoint scheme is significantly more detailed, using 39 different keypoints including multiple keypoints for the tail, the back and especially for the face region. [Banik, Li, and Dong, 2021]

For dairy farms, datasets for a bird’s eye view setting already exist. This camera setting is only possible in large barns with high ceilings. CattleEyeView [Ong et al., 2023] is an exemplary dataset that has been constructed for Computer Vision-based livestock farming, including Pose Estimation annotations. However, due to the bird’s eye perspective, only a limited set of keypoints is usually visible. For example, the keypoints of feet and knees are usually obscured by the body, leading to poor Pose Estimation performance [Ong et al., 2023].

Most publications publish a score on the AP-10K dataset as a reference on how well their model works for animal data. Besides, published models usually provide built-in support for the AP-10K keypoint scheme. Moreover, the AP-10K dataset requires fewer computational resources than larger datasets such as APTv2 and Animal Kingdom. For these reasons, AP-10K is chosen in this work when fine-tuning with domain-specific datasets (see Chapter 4). Identifying and filtering animals that closely resemble cows to reduce the domain gap instead of taking the entire dataset is left for future work.

A standard procedure is to pre-train animal pose estimators on human Pose Estimation datasets. Most commonly, the COCO dataset is used for that. This dataset includes a variety of objects and annotations for different Computer Vision tasks. A

subset of this dataset, COCO-Pose, includes humans in various settings with annotated keypoints. This subset is usually used for pre-training. [Lin et al., 2015]

3.2 Established Pose Estimation Models

In this section, being state-of-the-art pose estimators, ViTPose, RTMPose and RTMO are described in detail. A high-level comparison of these three models can be found in Table 3.1.

	ViTPose++-l	RTMPose-m	RTMO-l*
Prediction paradigm (see Section 2.3.2)	2D heatmap-based regression	Independent 1D classifications (fixed bin count)	Independent 1D classifications (dynamic bins)
Architecture	ViT	CNN	CNN
Parameters	307M	14M	45M
Real-time capability	No	Yes	Yes
AP-10K mAP (animal domain) with additional training datasets	80.4 AIC, APT-36K, COCO-Pose, MPII, WholeBody	72.2 AIC, COCO-Pose	-
CrowdPose mAP (human domain) with additional training datasets	76.6 AIC, COCO-Pose, MPII	70.6 AIC, COCO-Pose	83.8 AIC, COCO-Pose, Halpe, JHMDB, MPII, PoseTrack18

TABLE 3.1: High-level comparison of established Pose Estimation models

The key difference between the models is the underlying prediction paradigm (see Section 2.3.2). ViTPose follows a regression-based approach, where the model generates 2D heatmaps for each keypoint, effectively treating coordinates as a continuous value. In contrast, RTMPose and RTMO use a classification-based approach. Instead of regressing continuous coordinates, these models discretize the image space into bins (either a fixed count, as in RTMPose, or dynamic, as in RTMO) and classify each keypoint location into one of those bins. Note that the classification is done independently for the x- and y-direction. This shifts the task from predicting a precise 2D location to selecting the most likely region along each axis, which is usually done to increase speed [Li et al., 2022].

The table further distinguishes performance across two domains: the animal domain and the human domain. The animal domain is represented by the AP-10K benchmark (see Section 3.1). The human domain is evaluated using CrowdPose, a dataset specifically designed for multi-person Pose Estimation in crowded scenes, making

it a challenging benchmark due to frequent occlusions and overlapping individuals [Li et al., 2019].

It is important to note that the reported performance scores are influenced by the amount of additional training data used. For instance, ViTPose achieves a high mAP of 80.4 on the AP-10K dataset, but this result benefits from training on a variety of additional datasets. Similarly, RTMO achieves 83.8 mAP on CrowdPose with extensive additional supervision from multiple Pose Estimation datasets. In contrast, RTMPose uses fewer supplementary datasets and generally has fewer parameters, which may partially explains its lower performance. Therefore, comparisons between models must be interpreted cautiously as differences in training data volume and diversity can significantly affect results. From this perspective, the performance scores do not reflect solely the model architecture or training strategy but also the richness of the training input.

Lastly, the table also highlights real-time capability. ViTPose, despite its strong accuracy, is not suitable for real-time applications due to its large size (307 million parameters) and computational cost. In contrast, both RTMPose and RTMO are designed with efficiency in mind, allowing deployment in real-time systems such as required for this work.

3.2.1 ViTPose

ViTPose achieves state-of-the-art performance on Animal Pose Estimation. This section serves to explain its Top-Down model architecture (see Section 2.3) as visualized in Figure 3.2.

FIGURE 3.2: ViTPose model architecture [Xu et al., 2023]

The idea of ViTPose is to apply plain Vision Transformers (see Section 2.1.2) to Pose Estimation tasks. Similar to a regular transformer, it is composed of an encoder and a decoder. The encoder's aim is to convert the input image into contextual representations. Every encoder block uses multi-head self-attention, Layer Normalization and an MLP. These blocks can be stacked L times (see Figure 3.2), where an increase in L models an increasing encoding complexity. The decoder is designed to decode the encoder's output into an overall model output, in this case keypoint heatmaps. [Xu et al., 2023]

As ViTPose is supposed to work for generic Pose Estimation tasks, it must be capable of handling different species with different keypoint categories and poses. This introduces several challenges. First, categories that are present in one dataset might be absent in another dataset using a different keypoint scheme. As described later in this subsection, this is handled by using distinct decoder heads for each keypoint scheme. Second, even if the same keypoint is present in all datasets, its appearance might differ significantly: A human nose looks different than a cow’s nose. Third, the spatial relation of keypoints differs across different species: The nose keypoint of a human is usually above the shoulder, while a cow, standing on four legs, has its head to the left or right of the shoulder. [Xu et al., 2023]

To address different feature types and spatial relations, ViTPose++ treats each body keypoint detection as a different task. The fully connected layers of the encoder are split into task-agnostic and task-specific layers as there is both shared and specific knowledge across different keypoint schemes. These layers differ in the data they see during training: the shared, task-agnostic layer is trained with all data, while the task-specific layers are each trained only on data from a particular keypoint scheme. This process is visualized in Figure 3.3. [Xu et al., 2023]

FIGURE 3.3: The Mixture of Expert approach applied in ViTPose++ [Xu et al., 2023]

F^{FFN} denotes the output of the multi-head self-attention block. Freezing different parts of the model when fine-tuning (see Section 2.1.3), [Xu et al., 2023] show that the multi-head self-attention block is not sensitive to the underlying Pose Estimation task but it is the fully connected layer that is responsible for modeling task-specific properties. F^{FFN} is fed into a task-agnostic and T task-specific layers, one for each task. The encoder’s output is a concatenation of the shared and the specific layer. [Xu et al., 2023]

Unlike traditional transformer architectures, ViTPose++ employs a lightweight, task-specific convolutional decoder tailored for Pose Estimation. The structure of the decoder is shown in Figure 3.4.

The decoder transforms the encoder’s rich feature representation, which contains both shared and task-specific information, into a set of keypoint heatmaps. The deconvolution (Deconv) layers transpose the process outlined in Figure 2.4, increasing

FIGURE 3.4: ViTPose decoder structure [Xu et al., 2023]

the spatial resolution. Batch Normalization (BN), i.e., normalizing each input feature within each batch of training samples, stabilizes the training process. The ReLU activation (see Equation 2.3) introduces non-linearity, enabling the model to capture more complex patterns. The predictor consists of a simple 1×1 convolution that merges the feature channels to produce the final heatmaps. The authors of the paper found that even when using a predictor only, the performance remains strong, showcasing the robustness of the transformer’s encoder. [Xu et al., 2023]

Each task has its own dedicated decoder head tailored to its specific keypoint scheme, although all decoders share the same encoder output as input. For instance, there is one decoder head for the AP-10K keypoint scheme, and another one for CrowdPose keypoints. Taking AP-10K with 17 keypoints as an example, the respective decoder head outputs 17 heatmaps, one per keypoint. [Xu et al., 2023]

The ViTPose model family composes models in different sizes, i.e., the number of encoder layers as well as the feature dimensions can be scaled to meet individual requirements. On the AP-10K test set, the largest reported model ViTPose++-H (see Table 3.2) achieves state-of-the-art performance with an mAP score of 82.4. It is important to note that this model has been not only trained on AP-10K, but additionally on the AIC [Wu et al., 2019], APT-36K [Yang et al., 2022], COCO-Pose [Lin et al., 2014], COCO WholeBody [Jin et al., 2020] and MPII [Andriluka et al., 2014] datasets. Besides, the reported score is evaluated based on keypoint predictions made for ground truth bounding box crops. This is optimistic as in practice the required object detector will likely not perfectly detect all objects. [Xu et al., 2023]

3.2.2 RTMPose

In contrast to ViTPose, RTMPose achieves real-time compatibility, focusing on inference speed rather than accuracy only. The Top-Down architecture of RTMPose is outlined in Figure 3.5.

RTMPose adapts the Simple Coordinate Classification (SimCC) approach [Li et al., 2022] which introduced the idea of treating the two axes of an image as two independent classification problems instead of performing 2D heatmap-based regression (see Section 2.3.2). First, features are extracted by using a CNN-based backbone.

FIGURE 3.5: RTMPose model architecture [Yang et al., 2023]

Then, for each keypoint, SimCC treats x and y coordinates as independent classification problems. Each axis is discretized into bins to then predict the probability distribution for the respective keypoint over these bins. [Li et al., 2022]

The model is trained to predict Gaussian-like distributions by applying Gaussian label smoothing. Instead of using a hard label that assigns 1 to the labeled pixel and 0 to all other pixels, the idea of Gaussian label smoothing is to spread the probability mass centered around the annotated pixel as it makes sense to assign close pixels a higher probability than far ones. As Gaussian distributions are unimodal, the expected value of the predicted distribution can be used to obtain the keypoint coordinate. [Li et al., 2022]

To measure how the predicted distribution Q differs from the target distribution P (obtained by Gaussian label smoothing), the Kullback-Leibler Divergence (KLD) is chosen as the model's loss function: [Kullback and Leibler, 1951]

$$D_{\text{KL}}(P \parallel Q) = \sum_x P(x) \log \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)}. \quad (3.1)$$

Treating the two-dimensional probability distribution as two independent 1D distributions ($P(x \cap y) = P(x)P(y)$) has implications on the performance. The advantage of this approach is that instead of requiring $X \times Y$ output neurons, only $X + Y$ neurons are required. This is computationally much more efficient, which is especially crucial when focusing on real-time capability. However, this simplification is mathematically incorrect. Theoretically, it might be that the maximum probability of the independently treated classification problems differs from the maximum of the 2D probability distribution. In practice, this simplification usually yields reasonable results.

SimCC serves as a baseline for the RTMPose model. As the focus is on inference speed, the ResNet-50 backbone proposed by SimCC is replaced by a more lightweight CPSNext-m network. Besides, the upsampling layers used for a resolution increase in SimCC are removed in the RTMPose model. These adaptations lead to a slight mAP decrease of 1% but drastically reduce the model size. [Yang et al., 2023]

Several steps have been taken to further improve the SimCC baseline. For instance, different kernel sizes of the last CNN layer have been tried, ending up with a 7×7 instead of a 1×1 kernel. Moreover, inspired by transformers, a self-attention module is added after the CNN to learn not only local but also global context. As proposed by other publications such as ViTPose, additional datasets have been used for training to further boost the mAP score. [Yang et al., 2023]

The only reported mAP score on the AP-10K test set is 72.2, achieved by the second-largest model RTMPose-m when pre-training on the AIC and COCO-Pose datasets [Yang et al., 2023]. The question arises whether the lag of about 10 mAP points compared to ViTPose is due to the model architecture or rather due to fewer training data (see Table 3.1). Therefore, in this thesis, all models that are compared in Chapters 4 and 5 are explicitly trained on the same datasets rather than using the official checkpoints to ensure comparability.

3.2.3 RTMO

In contrast to the models discussed above, RTMO follows a one-stage approach similar to the YOLO approach in Object Detection (see Section 2.2.1). The details on the model's architecture are visualized in Figure 3.6.

FIGURE 3.6: RTMO model architecture [Lu et al., 2024]

As usual for neural networks in Computer Vision, the CNN in the backbone is used to extract low-level features such as sharp lines from the image. In the neck¹, two spatial feature maps are derived from different backbone stages. This multi-scale representation helps to detect both rough and fine scale features. Each of the two feature maps has its own head. [Lu et al., 2024]

Each model head can be further divided into two branches: one for the score and one for the pose and bounding box prediction. The score branch predicts the confidence score for each cell, i.e., how likely it is to contain an object. The second branch predicts the bounding box as well as the keypoint coordinates. It is not explained

¹Note: It is called the neck of the network as it is the part between the network's backbone and head, not to be confused with the neck keypoint.

how the Object Detection mechanism actually works in this model, it is only referred to the YOLO architecture (see Section 2.2.1). [Lu et al., 2024]

For Pose Estimation, the unique feature of this model is the Dynamic Coordinate Classifier. First, as an adaptation to the RTMPose approach, a *dynamic* bin allocation is used. Dynamic here refers to the varying number of bins per bounding box, with the aim of keeping the bin size static. As a result, the resolution is kept at a similar level: The larger the object, the more bins are allocated. Using an extended region around the detected bounding box to allow for tolerance, the area is divided into bins along the axes relative to the size of the bounding box. These bins are encoded with positions to model spatial information, similar to what is done in Vision Transformers. Finally, one-dimensional heatmaps along the axes are generated to indicate the most probable keypoint location. This is visualized for the left elbow of the snowboarder in Figure 3.6. [Lu et al., 2024]

Inspired by SimCC, RTMO also uses soft labels. Instead of Gaussian label smoothing (see Section 3.2.2), Laplace label smoothing is chosen. Although the paper does not explain this choice, it is likely intended to enable more precise keypoint predictions, since the Laplace distribution assigns higher probability density near the mean compared to a Gaussian with the same variance. [Lu et al., 2024]

Instead of using KLD as in RTMPose (see Section 3.2.2), the idea of RTMO is to explicitly model uncertainty of keypoint predictions by using Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE). The target distribution of the predictions given the smoothed labels can be defined as:

$$p_k(x_i | \mu_x) = \frac{1}{2b} \exp\left(-\frac{|x_i - \mu_x|}{b}\right) \sim \text{Laplace}(\mu_x, b), \quad (3.2)$$

where μ_x is set to the annotated x-coordinate under a Laplacian error and x_i represents the predicted keypoint k . The scale parameter b of the Laplacian distribution models the uncertainty in the annotation: A large b indicates high diversity, and therefore low confidence in the prediction x_i .

The aim of the discrete predictions $\hat{p}_k(x_i)$ is to model the true distribution of the annotations $P(\mu_x)$. Applying the law of total probability and considering the symmetry of the Laplacian distribution with respect to its mean, this likelihood can be written as

$$P(\mu_x) = \sum_{i=1}^{B_x} p_k(\mu_x | x_i) \hat{p}_k(x_i) = \sum_{i=1}^{B_x} p_k(x_i | \mu_x) \hat{p}_k(x_i) \quad (3.3)$$

where B_x denotes the number of bins. This is useful as Equation 3.2 can now be plugged into Equation 3.3. When designing a Loss function, constant factors may

be omitted as this does not affect the gradient. This also holds for monotonic transforms. Maximizing the likelihood in Equation 3.3 is equal to minimizing the negative log-likelihood that can be expressed by the following equation:

$$\mathcal{L}_{mle}^{(x)} = -\log \left[\sum_{i=1}^{B_x} \frac{1}{b} \exp \left(-\frac{|x_i - \mu_x|}{b} \right) \hat{p}_k(x_i) \right]. \quad (3.4)$$

In RTMO, however, a slightly adapted version of this Loss function is used:

$$\mathcal{L}_{mle}^{(x)} = -\log \left[\sum_{i=1}^{B_x} \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}} \exp \left(-\frac{|x_i - \mu_x|}{2\hat{\sigma}s} \right) \hat{p}_k(x_i) \right]. \quad (3.5)$$

Note that for normalization, there is an additional variable s that denotes the bounding box size. The factor 2 in the denominator of the exponential is not justified in the paper. Instead of the scale b that is usually used in the Laplace notation, the paper uses $\hat{\sigma}$ which refers to the predicted variance. How this variance is predicted remains unclear. [Lu et al., 2024]

Assuming independence between x and y (as in RTMPose), the total MLE loss becomes the sum of the above equation in x and y direction: [Lu et al., 2024]

$$\mathcal{L}_{mle} = \mathcal{L}_{mle}^{(x)} + \mathcal{L}_{mle}^{(y)} \quad (3.6)$$

The authors of RTMO have only published results on Human Pose Estimation. On the CrowdPose dataset, it clearly outperforms both RTMPose and ViTPose (see Table 3.1). Again, the comparison is to be used with caution due to the difference in training data. In addition to the training datasets used in ViTPose, it has been trained on Halpe [Fang et al., 2022], JHMDB [Jhuang et al., 2013] and PoseTrack18 [Andriluka et al., 2018]. Either way, RTMO seems promising for Animal Pose Estimation as well and is therefore further evaluated in the next chapter.

3.2.4 Model comparison

Based on the model architectures, several technical differences between the models can be derived. An overview of the respective strengths and weaknesses for the three models is given in Table 3.2.

One key difference lies in how keypoint coordinates are represented. ViTPose++ uses continuous 2D heatmaps, where a separate heatmap is generated per keypoint. This allows for precise predictions but comes with higher computational costs and memory usage. In contrast, both RTMPose and RTMO adopt an independent 1D classification approach, where the x - and y -coordinates are predicted separately as

Model	Strengths	Weaknesses
ViTPose++	High accuracy: 2D heatmaps with continuous pixels	Slow inference
	Transferability due to MoE	Data-hungry
		Reliance on object detector
RTMPose	Attention additional to CNN: Local and global context	Accuracy on a grid level, no exact location
	Efficient due to approximation	Inaccuracy due to independence assumption
		Reliance on object detector
RTMO	Dynamic binning handles different object sizes	Accuracy on a grid level, no exact location
	Efficient due to approximation	Inaccuracy due to independence assumption
	Strong performance on human datasets	Not tested on animal Pose Estimation tasks
	Uncertainty modeling	More training data required for probabilistic modeling
	No object detector required	

TABLE 3.2: Expected technical model strengths and weaknesses

probability distributions over discretized bins. While this is computationally efficient, assuming independence and predicting on a grid level may introduce inaccuracy.

In terms of training complexity, ViTPose++ generally requires more data than real-time models like RTMPose and RTMO. When trained on insufficient data, it tends to overfit due to its large number of parameters. However, with adequate data, it demonstrates strong transferability across datasets, thanks to its task-agnostic and task-specific layers. In contrast, RTMPose and RTMO adopt a simplified modeling approach by treating x- and y-coordinate predictions as independent variables, which significantly reduces the number of parameters. This makes them more efficient when trained on smaller datasets. Another key feature of RTMO is its explicit modeling of uncertainty. Since no prediction is ever flawless, estimating the level of uncertainty provides valuable insight into the reliability of each keypoint. However, this only works with enough training data.

While the accuracy of both RTMO and RTMPose is on a grid level, RTMO ensures that each grid cell is equally sized by employing a dynamic binning strategy. RTMPose, in contrast, uses a fixed number of bins per bounding box, which results in different spatial resolutions depending on the object size.

Another major distinction is that both ViTPose++ and RTMPose perform Pose Estimation only, requiring an additional Object Detection model. Due to its one-stage architecture, RTMO is both an object detector and a pose estimator at once. This is of high value in terms of inference time, as both tasks are simultaneously solved in

real-time. Even though solving both tasks at once is more challenging, results on human datasets show strong performance. It is to be evaluated whether this also holds for the animal domain.

4 Methodology for Pose Estimation of Dairy Cows

Based on theoretical foundations, this chapter presents the different methods used to accurately estimate the poses of dairy cows. First, the manually labeled barn dataset is described. This is followed by a discussion of different training approaches.

4.1 Barn Dataset Overview

To obtain a custom Pose Estimation dataset tailored for small dairy farms, recordings of 17 test farms are used. For all 51 available cameras, images are sampled hourly at daytime and every three hours at night, as less action is expected during the night. 500 images composing 2855 objects in total have been annotated with bounding boxes and keypoints using the AP-10K keypoint scheme, which is visualized in Figure 1.2.

As described in Section 3.1, the AP-10K keypoint scheme composes 17 keypoints. When labeling these keypoints, the following questions arise:

1. **Which keypoints are to be labeled?** As suggested by public datasets like AP-10K: Only visible keypoints. In Figure 1.2, the right hip is marked in gray as it is only labeled for the sake of completeness and would not be labeled in practice. Keypoints that are occluded by either the cow itself or another object are to be ignored as they can only be guessed. It is to be noted that keypoint annotations without connections (due to occlusions of the connecting keypoints) can occur and are equally permitted.
2. **Where to set each of the keypoints?** The eyes, the nose and the root of tail keypoints are unambiguous, their position is straightforward. Each leg has three keypoints: the hoof which is to be placed at the bottom of the leg, the elbow or knee which is to be labeled at the center joint of the leg and the shoulder or hip which is defined to be at the base of the leg. When placing the neck keypoint, this might look different from different perspectives. The idea here is to set it in the middle of the neck, regardless of the perspective. However, it is difficult to consistently place the neck keypoints, which is why slight variations across different neck keypoints are unavoidable.

These labeling guidelines have been provided for all annotators. Using Supervisely¹, the state-of-the-art ViTPose++-h model was used to generate labeling suggestions. Depending on the confidence threshold that can be set by the user, more or less model predictions are shown. As it is easier to delete keypoints than adding a new skeleton from scratch, this confidence threshold has been chosen to be rather low: All keypoints with a confidence of greater than 0.3 are shown. Hence, many invisible keypoints are suggested that must be deleted by the user. As the bounding boxes for these images have already been annotated in a previous labeling task, these are considered the ground truth (even though there might be inaccuracies). An exemplary image showing these suggestions is given in Figure 4.1.

FIGURE 4.1: Labeling suggestions of an exemplary barn image

This image visualizes several challenges. First of all, even for less than ten cows, the scene becomes crowded and confusing quickly. To handle this, the user can zoom in and out, allowing a more detailed view. A screenshot of the user interface is provided in Figure 4.4. To keep track of the individual keypoints, the user can fade in the names of each keypoint. The area which is zoomed into is indicated in the top right hand corner. This is particularly important in scenes that are even more crowded, such as pictured in Figure 4.5. Another problem occurs due to unfavorable light conditions, especially for infrared images that are taken during the night. Figure 4.6 shows a barn image where this problem is even more severe, where the cows on the left-hand side are only rarely visible.

When annotating, each keypoint suggestion is to be reviewed. In case of occlusions, the respective keypoint is to be deleted. Inaccurate predictions can be dragged to their actual position. The labeled image at the end of the labeling process is shown in Figure 4.2.

¹<https://supervisely.com>

FIGURE 4.2: Labeled barn image

Occlusions are probably the biggest challenge in labeling. While Figure 4.2 mainly shows keypoints occluded by the object itself, multiple other types of occlusion occur in the barn dataset, e.g. occlusions by fences (see Figure 4.6), partition walls (see Figure 4.3) and metal pillars or struts (see Figure 4.2 and 4.5). This is challenging not only during labeling, but also for the model, as it has to learn that these striking horizontal and vertical lines are irrelevant for the keypoints.

FIGURE 4.3: Overall view of another labeled barn image

To train and evaluate with this dataset, two different dataset splits are used in this work: a **random split** and a **barn split**. When splitting the images at random, the model has most likely seen all barns during training, making it easier to handle the characteristics of these known settings during inference. To evaluate the model's performance on new barns, a barn split having different barns in the test set than in the training set is appropriate. This is discussed in more detail in the out-of-domain experiment in Section 5.2.

FIGURE 4.4: Detailed view with keypoint tags

FIGURE 4.5: Exemplary barn image of a crowded scene

To compare different models and training approaches, the random split is sufficient. Even though this probably yields over-optimistic results as similar images from the same barns are in the training as well as in the test set, the setting is the same for all models. For the random split, the 500 images are randomly divided into 300 train (60%), 100 validation (20%) and 100 test (20%) images.

FIGURE 4.6: Exemplary barn image of an underexposed scene

4.2 Training Approaches

Different training approaches using different models and datasets are analyzed in this section. All approaches have been evaluated on the test set of the random split of the barn dataset. Figure 4.7 shows the four training approaches that are described in this section.

FIGURE 4.7: Visualization of the training approaches

All approaches share a pre-training of the backbone on the ImageNet dataset. By classifying a variety of objects, general concepts such as edges and shapes are learned in the first step (see Section 2.1.3). Using this pre-trained backbone, the focus is shifted to the actual task: Pose Estimation. This is done by using the COCO-Pose dataset which contains keypoint annotations for all images that include humans. These two steps are the base for the all four approaches. When fine-tuning, the entire network is adapted for all models, i.e., no layers are frozen (see Section 2.1.3).

To obtain a baseline, the barn dataset is evaluated on a model that has only been trained on public datasets (see blue track in Figure 4.7). As the task is animal Pose

Estimation, the AP-10K dataset has been used to train the model (additional to ImageNet and COCO-Pose). The results are presented in Section 4.2.1.

The annotated barn dataset is used for training in three different ways. First, the models are fine-tuned directly on the barn dataset after the pre-training on ImageNet and COCO-Pose, without using AP-10K (see orange track in Figure 4.7 and Section 4.2.2 for results). Second, an additional pre-training on AP-10K is integrated after the COCO-Pose pre-training (see green track in Figure 4.7 and Section 4.2.3 for results). Third, instead of training in distinct stages, a joint-training approach is evaluated where images of both AP-10K and the barn dataset are simultaneously used for training (see purple track in Figure 4.7 and Section 4.2.4 for results).

All models have been trained for 210 epochs with a training batch size of 16 and a validation batch size of 8. The learning rate schedules proposed by the papers have been used without adaptation. Even though the model losses look reasonable (see Section 5.1), tuning these hyperparameters might be beneficial for future improvements. A comparison of the learning rates during the 210 epochs of all three models is shown in Figure 4.8.

FIGURE 4.8: Learning rate schedules of the three models

It is important to note that Top-Down models can be evaluated in two ways:

1. Based on the ground truth objects (GT): The annotated bounding boxes are used for cropping. This score would be reached with a perfect object detector.
2. Based on the actual object detections (OD): The detected bounding boxes are used for cropping. Using an object detector that has been trained on the same data as the pose estimator, this allows a fair comparison to Bottom-Up and one-stage models which may have a lower score due to inaccurate bounding box predictions that are part of the model and cannot be separated. In this work, the RTMDet-1 model has been used for Object Detection, achieving an mAP of 76% on the test barn dataset.

4.2.1 Baselines Using Public Datasets

To quantify the impact of the manually labeled barn dataset, training on COCO-Pose and AP-10K and evaluating on the custom barn dataset serves as a baseline. The scores are listed in Table 4.1.

Model	Evaluation	mAP	PCK
RTMO-1	-	19.3	28.6
RTMPose-m	OD-based	41.4	61.3
	GT-based	40.7	60.2
ViTPose+++-l	OD-based	53.4	73.6
	GT-based	54.8	72.5

TABLE 4.1: Performance baselines for barn dataset using only public datasets during training

ViTPose clearly outperforms the other models in this scenario. Especially the RTMO model struggles to estimate the dairy cow keypoints. What strikes the eye is that OD- and GT-based evaluation yield similar scores. Most likely, the bottleneck here is not the Object Detection but the Pose Estimation performance which is rather poor for all models. Regardless of how well the object is localized, the keypoint predictions are weak as none of the models was able to learn the domain knowledge of the custom dataset.

4.2.2 Barn Dataset Fine-Tuning

In the next step, the custom barn dataset is used for training. Even though the models have seen the ImageNet and the COCO-Pose dataset during pre-training, the only images in the fine-tuning stage are from the barn dataset. The results can be found in Table 4.2.

Model	Evaluation	mAP	PCK
RTMO-1	-	50.3	35.1
RTMPose-m	OD-based	62.3	76.9
	GT-based	72.9	76.9
ViTPose+++-l	OD-based	61.6	76.7
	GT-based	70.6	71.0

TABLE 4.2: Performance results for barn dataset fine-tuning (without AP-10K)

Surprisingly, when pre-trained on ImageNet and COCO-Pose only, RTMPose outperforms ViTPose. A reason for that could be that ViTPose needs a lot of data due to

a large number of tunable parameters, whereas RTMPose is more robust and data-efficient (see Section 3.2.4). All models have significantly profited from training on the custom dataset, which was expected.

As the domain knowledge can now be learned, evaluating based on the ground truth leads to much better mAP scores as the provided crops are simply more accurate. This does not hold for the PCK score. The PCK score works with binary decisions: Is the keypoint prediction close enough to the ground truth or not. This is highly sensitive to the size of the bounding box: If a bounding box much smaller than the actual object is predicted, fewer keypoints will be classified as correct. In contrast, the OKS-based mAP uses gradual penalties that even differ across keypoint categories, making it more reliable for interpretation.

4.2.3 Additional Pre-Training with Animal-Specific AP-10K Dataset

To enhance the small custom dataset with domain-specific images, the AP-10K dataset is used in addition to ImageNet and COCO-Pose. The first option is to add another stage of pre-training: The checkpoint from the training on COCO-Pose is used to then fine-tune on AP-10K, and this checkpoint is further used to finally fine-tune on the custom barn data. The results of the pre-training approach are shown in Table 4.3.

Model	Evaluation	mAP	PCK
RTMO-1	-	61.8	52.5
RTMPose-m	OD-based	61.1	77.4
	GT-based	70.7	77.7
ViTPose++-1	OD-based	63.8	80.2
	GT-based	73.3	80.9

TABLE 4.3: Performance results for barn dataset fine-tuning with additional pre-training on AP-10K

The effect of domain-specific pre-training varies significantly across models. RTMO shows the strongest improvement, likely due to its dynamic coordinate classification and probabilistic modeling, which allow it to adapt well to the new domain. ViTPose also benefits moderately, making use of its high model capacity. In contrast, RTMPose slightly decreases in accuracy. This may be explained by its bin-based classification approach, which can overfit to the spatial distribution of AP-10K’s keypoints and generalize less effectively to the barn dataset. In AP-10K, images often show only a single animal in high resolution, whereas the custom barn dataset contains several images of many small-scale cows. The crops of the small objects usually have a much lower resolution, potentially making it harder for RTMPose to accurately detect keypoints.

4.2.4 Joint-Training with AP-10K and Barn Dataset

Instead of pre-training with the AP-10K dataset, a joint-training approach might be beneficial. Joint-training means that, based on the COCO-Pose checkpoint, the model is fine-tuned on the custom barn dataset as well as on parts of the AP-10K dataset. This strategy allows the model to learn from both datasets simultaneously, rather than in sequential stages of pre-training and fine-tuning.

Heuristically, 500 random images of the AP-10K dataset are sampled to make sure the barn dataset still has enough weight. The evaluation is done on the barn data only. Table 4.4 provides the results for the joint-training approach.

Model	Evaluation	mAP	PCK
RTMO-1	-	51.3	36.3
RTMPose-m	OD-based	62.6	76.8
	GT-based	73.5	77.0
ViTPose+++-l	OD-based	62.3	77.2
	GT-based	71.2	78.0

TABLE 4.4: Performance results for fine-tuning on both the barn dataset and parts of AP-10K in a joint-training manner

None of the models has significantly improved compared to the previous approaches. A disadvantage of the implementation of this approach clearly is that, instead of 10 thousand images, only 500 are used. This shows room for improvement: Experimenting with different amounts of AP-10K data and oversampling the images from the custom barn dataset during the joint training will likely improve the results. However, due to time constraints, this has been left for future work. The results discussed in this chapter are summarized in Table 5.1.

5 Evaluation

In this chapter, the previously discussed models are compared with respect to quantitative and qualitative accuracy as well as inference speed. Besides, an out-of-domain experiment serves to evaluate the performance on new barns.

5.1 Pose Estimator Comparison on the Barn Dataset

In Chapter 4, different models and fine-tuning approaches have been compared. Table 5.1 gives a comprehensive overview of the results discussed so far. The joint-training approach (see Section 4.2.4) is denoted as (AP-10K* + barn data).

Model	Fine-tuning approach	Evaluation	mAP	PCK
RTMO-1	AP-10K	-	19.3	28.6
	barn data	-	50.3	35.1
	AP-10K + barn data	-	61.8	52.5
	(AP-10K* + barn data)	-	51.3	36.3
RTMPose-m	AP-10K	OD-based	41.4	61.3
		GT-based	40.7	60.2
	barn data	OD-based	62.3	76.9
		GT-based	72.9	76.9
	AP-10K + barn data	OD-based	61.1	77.4
		GT-based	70.7	77.7
	(AP-10K* + barn data)	OD-based	62.6	76.8
		GT-based	73.5	77.0
ViTPose+++-l	AP-10K	OD-based	53.4	73.6
		GT-based	54.8	72.5
	barn data	OD-based	61.6	76.7
		GT-based	70.6	71.0
	AP-10K + barn data	OD-based	63.8	80.2
		GT-based	73.3	80.9
	(AP-10K* + barn data)	OD-based	62.3	77.2
		GT-based	71.2	78.0

TABLE 5.1: Model scores across different fine-tuning approaches

The pre-training approach using the AP-10K dataset in a separate stage and then fine-tuning on the custom barn dataset works for all models. However, the RTMPose model works best when including only parts of the AP-10K images in a joint-training manner.

The validation losses of the three best models show convergence, indicating successful training (see Figure 5.1). While RTMPose and ViTPose converge smoothly, RTMO shows a sharp drop at epochs 105. This behavior can be explained by a change in the weighting of the individual losses for bounding box and keypoint detections from this epoch onward. Although not explicitly explained in the original paper, this strategy likely aims to prioritize Object Detection in the early training phase and subsequently shift focus toward refining keypoint localization in a second stage.

FIGURE 5.1: Validation losses of the best models during training

When comparing the best mAP scores for each model (see Table 5.1, high scores marked in bold), the gaps between the models are not as high as expected based on the reported scores from the publications. This can be traced back to the fact that all models have been trained on the same data and that the Top-Down models are evaluated based on actual object detections. This allows for a fair comparison between the models, showing that the real-time capable models can compete with the much larger ViTPose model.

As pure metrics make it hard to interpret Computer Vision performance, predictions for a sample barn image from the test set are shown for each model. The ground truth annotations can be found in Figure 4.2. It is to be noted that only bounding boxes and keypoints exceeding a certain confidence threshold are shown for better qualitative evaluation. For RTMO, RTMPose and ViTPose the model predictions are visualized in Figure 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4, respectively.

To describe deviations from the ground truth, differently colored arrows have been added:

- Green: False bounding box detection (False Positive or False Negative)
- Orange: Large distance between the ground truth and the predicted keypoint
- Blue: Prediction of invisible keypoints (False Positives)
- Red: Missing prediction of visible keypoint (False Negatives)

FIGURE 5.2: RTMO predictions for a sample barn image

It is clearly visible that the RTMO model tends to struggle with accurately detecting the objects. In this image, an additional cow is detected in the top right-hand corner (see smaller green rectangle over the head of the front cow). The actual cow in the background is not detected, possibly because most of the head and three out of four legs are occluded. In terms of keypoint detection, some predictions are slightly off, especially when focusing on the leg keypoints where the predictions are sometimes next to the actual body joints. This may be explained by the accuracy level which is limited to a grid instead of predicting continuous coordinates (see Section 3.2.4). Note that the deviation in the output image is several pixels, but this might be only one pixel in the reduced resolution at the input of the network, so sub-pixel accuracy becomes crucial.

As already clarified in Chapter 4, to allow for a fair comparison, the RTMDet-1 object detector used for the Top-Down approaches is trained on the same datasets as the pose estimators. Inspecting Figure 5.3 and 5.4, the extra Object Detection model tends to perform better than the one-stage approach of RTMO.

Focusing on Pose Estimation, the keypoints predicted by RTMPose and ViTPose look slightly more accurate than the RTMO predictions. Regarding the leg keypoints again, the predictions are less off. This is surprising as similar to RTMO, the keypoint representations are grid-based, and x and y are assumed to be independent. It might be that RTMO struggles to model uncertainty effectively due to an insufficient amount of training data, resulting in keypoints drifting away from the ground truth.

FIGURE 5.3: RTMPose predictions for a sample barn image

FIGURE 5.4: ViTPose predictions for a sample barn image

While RTMO tends to predict more False Positives, RTMPose and ViTPose seem to struggle with False Negatives. However, this insight should be treated with caution, as changing the confidence threshold has a direct impact on the trade-off between False Positives and False Negatives: The higher this threshold is chosen, the less False Positives, but the more False Negatives will appear. Comparing RTMPose and ViTPose, the performance seems comparable based on qualitative inspection.

As inference speed is of special interest for this application, the inference time per frame has been measured on a CPU (see Appendix A for details on the test environment). Table 5.2 provides the inference time averaged over 500 frames.

Model	Task	Inference time [s]
RTMO-l	OD & PE	0.395
RTMDet-l	OD	0.414
RTMDet-l & RTMPose-m	OD & PE	0.634
RTMDet-l & ViTPose++-l	OD & PE	3.207

TABLE 5.2: Comparison of mean inference times per frame on CPU

As expected, the RTMO model outperforms the other approaches in terms of inference speed. It is even faster than RTMDet-1 performing Object Detection only. As required for Top-Down Pose Estimators in practice, it only makes sense to evaluate their inference speed in combination with an Object Detector. It becomes clear that when using ViTPose, significantly fewer frames can be analyzed, leading to highly discontinuous observations.

5.2 Out-of-Domain Performance

The previous scores have all been evaluated on a random split of the barn dataset. When deploying the model at new barns, this performance is optimistic as it has not seen the specific barn setting during training (see Section 4.1). Ideally, no additional fine-tuning with new, labeled data of this new barn should be required, but the model should be able to generalize beyond specific barn settings. To evaluate whether this requirement is met, an out-of-domain experiment is set up to obtain the trend of the domain gap. The data is split by barns as visualized in Figure 5.5.

FIGURE 5.5: Barn split visualization

The dataset is divided into two groups: Out-of-domain (OOD) and In-domain (ID) barns. When indexing the barns, the number of cows per barn has been taken into account to obtain comparable groups. Importantly, the training sets shown in Figure 5.5 are not fixed, but samples are drawn from these sets. This is done in the following two settings:

1. OOD Performance: The validation and test set contains only barns that have not been used during OOD training. There is no barn overlap between the OOD training set and the validation and test set (see Figure 5.5). From the OOD training set, different combinations of 1 to 6 barns are drawn, which is

explained later in this section. For each subset, a model is trained and evaluated on the same validation and test set to obtain a performance trend along with the number of barns used during training.

2. ID Performance: To compare the OOD trend to the ID trend, an ID training set of a similar size to the OOD training set is used. This includes images from the same barns that are used for the validation and test set (see Figure 5.5). The ID trend is obtained by drawing random subsets containing different numbers of cows from the in-domain training set. Again, for each subset, a model is trained and evaluated on the same validation and test set as in the OOD setting before, ensuring comparability across all models.

To compare the OOD to the ID trend, it is desired to construct two training sets of the same size, i.e., the out-of-domain training set should comprise approximately the same number of cows as the in-domain training set. Assuming an equal distribution of images and cows per farmer and given a 60:20:20 split into ID training, validation and test, the ideal barn split point can be obtained by comparing the areas in Figure 5.5: The equally sized training sets are of size 60×100 (and 100×60 , respectively). Having a total area of 100×160 and 17 barns, the ideal split point is at 6 ($17 \times \frac{60}{160} = 6.375$). Hence, 6 barns have been chosen to be in the OOD training set and the remaining 11 barns are used to construct the ID training set as well as the validation and test sets.

The model performance is expected to depend on two things:

1. The number of cows the model has been trained on. The more cows, the better the performance.
2. The number of different barns the model has seen during training. It can be assumed that the more settings a model has been trained on, the better it is able to generalize beyond these settings.

The goal of this experiment is to find empirical evidence that these two aspects determine the model's performance. This is done using the RTMPose model. Even though similar behavior is expected for RTMO and ViTPose, this assumption has not been empirically validated within the scope of this work and could be addressed in future research.

To show the influence of the number of barns seen during training, several runs with the out-of-domain training set including a different number of barns are executed. It is expected that for all 6 barns, the performance is closer to the in-domain performance than for 1 barn.

As the barns differ in the number of cows, lighting conditions, ceiling heights, etc., the Pose Estimation performance will also be different across barns depending on how complex the setting of the barn is. Therefore, it is crucial to train with different barn combinations. For 1 barn, 6 runs including 1 barn each in the out-of-domain

training set are executed. Including all 6 barns results in another training run. For 2 to 5 barns, the number of combinations quickly becomes large, for instance, $\binom{6}{3} = 20$ runs would in theory be required to include all combinations for 3 barns. To reduce computational costs, for 2 to 5 barns, only 6 combinations are drawn from all possible combinations. Hence, the experiment includes $6 + 4 * 6 + 1 = 31$ runs for obtaining the out-of-domain trend.

For the in-domain trend, 10 models are trained using different proportions of the ID training set. For the first model, 10% of the ID set is used, then 20% for the second model, and so on. Only the last model uses the entire ID training set (100%). Figure 5.6 shows the mAP score of each model based on the number of cows and barns it has been trained on.

FIGURE 5.6: Out-of-domain in comparison to in-domain performance

The circles show all models that have been trained using an out-of-domain training set where the color indicates the number of included barns. The average for all OOD points using the same number of barns is marked with an \times . Triangular data points denote in-domain training runs. Fitting a logarithmic regression line through both in- and out-of-domain points, it can be seen that the out-of-domain trend approaches the in-domain trend. In other words, there is strong evidence for both assumptions: The mAP score increases with an increasing number of cows and barns. Practically, this is important as when training the model on many test barns, it should be able to generalize in a new setting, i.e., when deploying the model at a new farm.

5.3 Reconciliation of the Requirements

Concluding the thesis, this section checks the Pose Estimation models against the previously defined requirements. Table 5.3 shows an overview of the committed requirements and whether these have been fully met (✓) or there are still steps to be taken (✗).

ID	Requirement	Fulfilled?
R1	Multi-object handling	✓
R2	Real-time compatibility	✓
R3	High accuracy	✗
R4	Generalizability	✓
R5	Cost-efficiency	✓
R6	Extensibility	✓

TABLE 5.3: Reconciliation of the requirements based on the results

Three models have been evaluated for applying Pose Estimation to small dairy farms: ViTPose, RTMPose and RTMO. All models are capable of handling multiple objects, either in a single stage like RTMO or in a two-stage Top-Down manner like RTMPose and ViTPose (**R1**). Both RTMO and RTMPose are designed for real-time applications which could be shown by relatively fast inference times (**R2**). Whether analyzing two images per second is sufficiently fast depends on the specific downstream task. If faster predictions are required, using a GPU instead of a CPU might be already sufficient.

When it comes to accuracy (**R3**), there is room for improvement. Even though the predictions are reasonable in most cases, the performance could be boosted by training on more public datasets and by increasing the size of the manually labeled barn dataset. This is particularly important when classifying health statuses based on the pose, which requires accurate keypoint detections.

However, even with the small custom dataset, the out-of-domain experiment has shown the ability of the RTMPose model to generalize beyond specific settings, making the model deployable in practice when trained on a sufficient amount of different barns (**R4**). Having labeled only 500 images, the labeling costs could be kept low (**R5**). All approaches discussed can be extended by additional models or datasets, making it easy to improve the model’s performance in the future (**R6**).

6 Conclusion and Outlook

6.1 Summary

This thesis explored the feasibility of applying real-time Pose Estimation models to monitor dairy cows in small-scale farm environments using camera-only systems. After outlining the theoretical foundations of Pose Estimation and its relevance in livestock farming, the work evaluated three state-of-the-art models (ViTPose, RTMPose, and RTMO) using various training strategies on public and custom datasets.

A novel, manually annotated barn dataset based on real-world farm footage was created to bridge the domain gap between generic animal pose datasets and the specific conditions of small dairy barns. In the following, the research questions posed in Section 1.2 are answered using the results of this work.

How do public and custom datasets impact the performance of Pose Estimation models, particularly in domain-specific tasks?

Using public datasets is essential to train Pose Estimation models, especially when the target dataset is small. As extensively discussed, the amount and diversity of datasets used for training a model have a huge impact on the model's performance. While the comparison of the publicly reported model scores is unfair due to large training data variations, this thesis provides a fair comparison between the discussed models. Using the same training datasets, the real-time capable models RTMPose and RTMO are competitive with the state-of-the-art ViTPose model in this work.

Another conclusion that can be drawn from the experiments is that custom datasets are crucial for performing on domain-specific tasks. Without the manually labeled dataset, none of the models managed to properly estimate the keypoints. However, thanks to public datasets, fine-tuning on a small dataset is already sufficient to achieve reasonable results.

Are the Pose Estimation models able to generalize beyond specific environments, i.e., is the out-of-domain trend approaching the in-domain trend?

The domain gap experiment showed that the Pose Estimation model generalizes well beyond specific settings. Using only six barns during out-of-domain training, the gap between in- and out-of-domain performance significantly decreased compared to using one barn. As the out-of-domain trend approaches the in-domain

trend, it can be expected that when trained on a sufficient number of barns, a pose estimator will perform well even at new, unseen barns.

How well does RTMO perform on non-human keypoint detection?

While the authors of the RTMO paper have not published any scores on animal datasets, this thesis found that the model architecture is suitable for animal Pose Estimation when fine-tuning on animal datasets. On the custom barn dataset, it achieves an mAP just 0.8 percentage points lower than RTMPose. From qualitative inspections, it could be concluded that it sometimes lacks in properly detecting objects and that its keypoint detections are sometimes less accurate compared to the other models.

In theory, the performance can be improved by just providing more data. However, labeling poses is extremely time-consuming. In contrast, boosting the object detector used for the Top-Down approaches by providing additional bounding box labels is much easier. As shown in Chapter 4 and 5, the Pose Estimation performance of Top-Down models improves with better Object Detection. From this point of view, it may be argued that the RTMO model, having a built-in object detector, is less practical than Top-Down models.

6.2 Future Work

Several steps can be taken to further improve the Pose Estimation accuracy. As usual, training on more data is expected to give better results. Besides, it might be beneficial to filter the AP-10K images to train with quadrupeds that are similar to cows only, i.e., filtering out animals such as monkeys, bats and squirrels. Especially for the joint-training approach where fewer images are used, this filtering probably leads to better results. Besides, for the joint-training approach, different weightings of the AP-10K and barn dataset images could be exploited. Oversampling the barn data set might be helpful to include more AP-10K images while maintaining the focus on the custom dataset.

As the custom dataset is small, it might help to freeze the first layers to prevent large models such as ViTPose from overfitting. Freezing the early layers, which typically capture low-level, general-purpose features like edges and textures, allows the model to retain its pretrained representational power while reducing the risk of overfitting to limited training data. This approach also reduces the number of trainable parameters, leading to faster convergence and improved stability during training.

When the Pose Estimation model is sufficiently accurate, it can be used for various scenarios. The most straightforward use-case would be to do activity classification for behavioral analysis. Informed Machine Learning seems promising as behavioral biology experts know which poses indicate certain behavior.

To be able to classify behavior based on poses, it would be beneficial to use a more detailed keypoint scheme. An indicator of lameness is not only asymmetries in leg movement but also a curved back [Tun et al., 2024]. Having multiple keypoints along the back is crucial for detecting lameness based on a curved back. To avoid losing the labeled data and public datasets that are based on the AP-10K scheme for training, a mapping between the new scheme and the AP-10K scheme has to be done. A common choice for this is to take the union of the keypoints of both schemes, such as done in [Yang et al., 2024]. Missing keypoints can be either ignored or imputed based on the spatial relation to other keypoints. However, this might introduce inaccurate labels, bearing the danger of mimicking the imputation rather than predicting the true location of the keypoint. Hence, it might be worth investing in additional labeling costs for unknown keypoints.

The findings of this work are likely transferable to other livestock species beyond dairy cows. This thesis presents a complete pipeline from dataset annotation to the development of trained Pose Estimation models. Depending on the specific use case, an appropriate model can be selected from state-of-the-art architectures by balancing the trade-off between accuracy and computational efficiency.

A Implementation Details

To ensure the reproducibility of the results presented in this thesis, the utilized tools, frameworks, and computing environments are described in the following.

A.1 Framework and Model Configuration

The experiments were conducted using the PyTorch-based open-source framework **MMPose**¹. MMPose provides ready-to-use configurations for all models employed in this thesis.

For instance, an example configuration file for the **RTMPose** model is available at the following link: https://github.com/open-mmlab/mmpose/blob/main/configs/animal_2d_keypoint/rtmpose/ap10k/rtmpose-m_8xb64-210e_ap10k-256x256.py.

In addition, model checkpoints trained on public datasets such as **COCO** and **AP-10K** have been provided to facilitate replication of the results. For example, an RTM-Pose checkpoint is accessible at: https://github.com/open-mmlab/mmpose/blob/main/configs/animal_2d_keypoint/rtmpose/README.md.

A.2 Evaluation and Tracking

The evaluation of model performance was conducted using the **pycocotools** library², which was employed to calculate the mAP scores of the respective models.

To monitor, compare, and track multiple models efficiently (as required in Section 5.2), the open-source tool **MLflow**³ was utilized. MLflow enabled effective experiment tracking, parameter logging, and result visualization.

¹<https://mmpose.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

²<https://github.com/cocodataset/cocoapi/tree/master/PythonAPI>

³<https://mlflow.org>

A.3 Computing Environment

All experiments on measuring inference speed (see Chapter 5) were conducted on a machine running **Ubuntu 24.04.1** with an **AMD Ryzen 7 5825U CPU**.

For model training, a **Kubernetes**⁴ cluster instance with a **NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU** was employed to ensure access to sufficient computing resources in a scalable cloud environment. This setup provided efficient resource management, allowing seamless training of large models across multiple nodes.

⁴<https://kubernetes.io>

Bibliography

- Adaloglou, Nikolas (2020). *Understanding the receptive field of deep convolutional networks*. Accessed: 2025-06-03. URL: <https://theaisummer.com/receptive-field/>.
- Alammar, Jay and Maarten Grootendorst (Sept. 2024). *Hands-On Large Language Models*. Beginner to intermediate level; estimated time to complete: 10h 29m. O'Reilly Media, Inc., p. 428.
- Andriluka, Mykhaylo et al. (2014). "2D Human Pose Estimation: New Benchmark and State of the Art Analysis". In: *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*.
- Andriluka, Mykhaylo et al. (2018). *PoseTrack: A Benchmark for Human Pose Estimation and Tracking*. arXiv: 1710.10000 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1710.10000>.
- Ba, Jimmy Lei, Jamie Ryan Kiros, and Geoffrey E. Hinton (2016). *Layer Normalization*. arXiv: 1607.06450 [stat.ML]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1607.06450>.
- Banik, Prianka, Lin Li, and Xishuang Dong (2021). *A Novel Dataset for Keypoint Detection of quadruped Animals from Images*. arXiv: 2108.13958 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2108.13958>.
- Barge, P. et al. (2013). "Radio frequency identification technologies for livestock management and meat supply chain traceability". In: *Canadian Journal of Animal Science* 93.1, pp. 23–33. DOI: 10.4141/cjas2012-029. URL: <https://doi.org/10.4141/cjas2012-029>.
- Baxter, Jonathan (1995). "Learning internal representations". In: *Proceedings of the eighth annual conference on Computational learning theory - COLT '95*. COLT '95. ACM Press, 311–320. DOI: 10.1145/225298.225336. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/225298.225336>.
- Bengio, Yoshua et al. (2011). "Deep Learners Benefit More from Out-of-Distribution Examples". In: *Proceedings of the Fourteenth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*. Ed. by Geoffrey Gordon, David Dunson, and Miroslav Dudík. Vol. 15. Proceedings of Machine Learning Research. Fort Lauderdale, FL, USA: PMLR, pp. 164–172. URL: <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v15/bengio11b.html>.
- Burger, Wilhelm and Mark J. Burge (2016). *Digital Image Processing: An Algorithmic Introduction Using Java*. 2nd ed. London: Springer. ISBN: 978-1-4471-6683-4. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4471-6684-1.

- Cao, Jinkun et al. (2019). *Cross-Domain Adaptation for Animal Pose Estimation*. arXiv: 1908.05806 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.05806>.
- Carion, Nicolas et al. (2020). *End-to-End Object Detection with Transformers*. arXiv: 2005.12872 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.12872>.
- CattleEye (2025). *CattleEye: Autonomous Livestock Monitoring*. Accessed: 2025-03-10. URL: <https://cattleeye.com>.
- Deng, Jia et al. (2009). *ImageNet: A large-scale hierarchical image database*. DOI: 10.1109/CVPR.2009.5206848.
- Dosovitskiy, Alexey et al. (2021). *An Image is Worth 16x16 Words: Transformers for Image Recognition at Scale*. arXiv: 2010.11929 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.11929>.
- Fang, Hao-Shu et al. (2022). *AlphaPose: Whole-Body Regional Multi-Person Pose Estimation and Tracking in Real-Time*. arXiv: 2211.03375 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.03375>.
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (1966). "Agriculture and industrialization". In: *The State of Food and Agriculture 1966*. United Nations, pp. 75–135. URL: <https://www.un-ilibrary.org/content/books/9789210472821c004>.
- Frochte, Jörg (2018). *Maschinelles Lernen*. Carl Hanser Verlag.
- Girshick, Ross et al. (2014). *Rich feature hierarchies for accurate object detection and semantic segmentation*. arXiv: 1311.2524 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1311.2524>.
- Ho, Jonathan et al. (2019). *Axial Attention in Multidimensional Transformers*. arXiv: 1912.12180 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1912.12180>.
- Jhuang, Hueihan et al. (2013). "Towards Understanding Action Recognition". In: *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*.
- Jiang, Tao et al. (2023). *RTMPose: Real-Time Multi-Person Pose Estimation based on MM-Pose*. arXiv: 2303.07399 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.07399>.
- Jin, Sheng et al. (2020). *Whole-Body Human Pose Estimation in the Wild*. arXiv: 2007.11858 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.11858>.
- Karn, Ujjwal (2016). *An Intuitive Explanation of Convolutional Neural Networks*. Accessed: 2025-06-01. URL: <https://ujjwalkarn.me/2016/08/11/intuitive-explanation-convnets/>.
- Kullback, S. and R. A. Leibler (1951). "On Information and Sufficiency". In: *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics* 22.1, pp. 79–86. DOI: 10.1214/aoms/1177729694. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1214/aoms/1177729694>.
- Kumar, Teerath et al. (2023). *Image Data Augmentation Approaches: A Comprehensive Survey and Future directions*. arXiv: 2301.02830 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.02830>.
- Li, Jiefeng et al. (2019). *CrowdPose: Efficient Crowded Scenes Pose Estimation and A New Benchmark*. arXiv: 1812.00324 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1812.00324>.

- Li, Yanjie et al. (2022). *SimCC: a Simple Coordinate Classification Perspective for Human Pose Estimation*. arXiv: 2107.03332 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2107.03332>.
- Lin, Brenda et al. (July 2011). "Effects of industrial agriculture on climate change and the mitigation potential of small-scale agro-ecological farms". In: *CAB Reviews: Perspectives in Agriculture, Veterinary Science, Nutrition, and Natural Resources* 6, pp. 1–18. DOI: 10.1079/PAVSNR20116020.
- Lin, Tsung-Yi et al. (2014). *Microsoft COCO: Common Objects in Context - Keypoints Evaluation*. Accessed: 2025-03-11. URL: <https://cocodataset.org/#keypoints-eval>.
- Lin, Tsung-Yi et al. (2015). *Microsoft COCO: Common Objects in Context*. arXiv: 1405.0312 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1405.0312>.
- Liu, Yang, Changzhen Qiu, and Zhiyong Zhang (Sept. 2024). "Deep learning for 3D human pose estimation and mesh recovery: A survey". In: *Neurocomputing* 596, p. 128049. ISSN: 0925-2312. DOI: 10.1016/j.neucom.2024.128049. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2024.128049>.
- Lu, Peng et al. (2024). *RTMO: Towards High-Performance One-Stage Real-Time Multi-Person Pose Estimation*. arXiv: 2312.07526 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.07526>.
- Lyu, Chengqi et al. (2022). *RTMDet: An Empirical Study of Designing Real-Time Object Detectors*. arXiv: 2212.07784 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.07784>.
- Manning, Christopher D., Prabhakar Raghavan, and Hinrich Schütze (2008). *Introduction to Information Retrieval*. Accessed: 2025-03-10. Cambridge University Press. URL: <https://nlp.stanford.edu/IR-book/pdf/irbookonlinereading.pdf>.
- MathWorks (2025). *MathWorks: Convolutional Neural Network*. Accessed: 2025-05-29. URL: <https://de.mathworks.com/discovery/convolutional-neural-network.html>.
- Ng, Xun Long et al. (2022). *Animal Kingdom: A Large and Diverse Dataset for Animal Behavior Understanding*. arXiv: 2204.08129 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2204.08129>.
- Ong, Kian Eng et al. (2023). *CattleEyeView: A Multi-task Top-down View Cattle Dataset for Smarter Precision Livestock Farming*. arXiv: 2312.08764 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.08764>.
- Phillips, Hunter (2023). *A Simple Introduction to Softmax*. Accessed: 2025-07-13. URL: <https://medium.com/@hunter-j-phillips/a-simple-introduction-to-softmax-287712d69bac>.
- Qazi, Ahmed, Taha Razzaq, and Asim Iqbal (2024). *AnimalFormer: Multimodal Vision Framework for Behavior-based Precision Livestock Farming*. arXiv: 2406.09711 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.09711>.
- Raghu, Maithra et al. (2022). *Do Vision Transformers See Like Convolutional Neural Networks?* arXiv: 2108.08810 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2108.08810>.

- Redmon, Joseph et al. (2016). *You Only Look Once: Unified, Real-Time Object Detection*. arXiv: 1506.02640 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1506.02640>.
- Stanford University (2025). *Stanford University: Deep Learning for Computer Vision*. Accessed: 2025-06-01. URL: <https://cs231n.github.io/convolutional-networks/#conv>.
- Tergast, H., H. Hansen, and E.-C. Weber (2022). "Steckbriefe zur Tierhaltung in Deutschland: Milchkühe". In: *Thünen Report*. Accessed: 2025-03-06. URL: https://literatur.thuenen.de/digbib_extern/dn065685.pdf.
- Tun, SC et al. (2024). "Revolutionizing Cow Welfare Monitoring: A Novel Top-View Perspective with Depth Camera-Based Lameness Classification". In: *J Imaging* 10.3, p. 67. DOI: 10.3390/jimaging10030067.
- Vaswani, Ashish et al. (2017). "Attention is All you Need". In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*. Ed. by I. Guyon et al. Vol. 30. Curran Associates, Inc. URL: https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2017/file/3f5ee243547dee91fbd053c1c4a845aa-Paper.pdf.
- Walchhofer, P. (2024). "Tracking and re-identification of dairy cows". Diploma Thesis. Technische Universität Wien. URL: <https://doi.org/10.34726/hss.2024.117386>.
- Wood, Luke and Francois Chollet (2022). *Efficient Graph-Friendly COCO Metric Computation for Train-Time Model Evaluation*. arXiv: 2207.12120 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.12120>.
- Wu, Jiahong et al. (July 2019). "Large-Scale Datasets for Going Deeper in Image Understanding". In: *2019 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME)*. IEEE. DOI: 10.1109/icme.2019.00256. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ICME.2019.00256>.
- Xu, Yufei et al. (2023). *ViTPose++: Vision Transformer for Generic Body Pose Estimation*. arXiv: 2212.04246 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.04246>.
- Yang, Jie et al. (2024). *X-Pose: Detecting Any Keypoints*. arXiv: 2310.08530 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.08530>.
- Yang, Yuxiang et al. (2022). *APT-36K: A Large-scale Benchmark for Animal Pose Estimation and Tracking*. arXiv: 2206.05683 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2206.05683>.
- Yang, Yuxiang et al. (2023). *APTv2: Benchmarking Animal Pose Estimation and Tracking with a Large-scale Dataset and Beyond*. arXiv: 2312.15612 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.15612>.
- Yosinski, Jason et al. (2014). *How transferable are features in deep neural networks?* arXiv: 1411.1792 [cs.LG]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1411.1792>.
- Yu, Hang et al. (2021). *AP-10K: A Benchmark for Animal Pose Estimation in the Wild*. arXiv: 2108.12617 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2108.12617>.
- Zou, Zhengxia et al. (2023). *Object Detection in 20 Years: A Survey*. arXiv: 1905.05055 [cs.CV]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1905.05055>.